

Roadmaps, White Paper and Value Added Reports

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Executive Summary

The EU-CIP project is dedicated to advancing the security and resilience of Europe's critical infrastructures by mapping the landscape of research, innovation, and technological development in Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP). Through systematic collection and analysis of information on CIP research areas, innovation activities, technological solutions, and standards, the project aims to provide actionable insights and strategic foresight for policymakers, industry, and the research community.

This inaugural report focuses on establishing a comprehensive overview of the current state of CIP in Europe, with a particular emphasis on EU-funded initiatives such as Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects. It highlights key technological areas, sectoral developments, and the outcomes of prominent research and innovation projects. Input has been gathered from a wide network of stakeholders, including project partners, critical infrastructure operators, solution vendors, and members of the European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures (ECSCI), ensuring a well-rounded and up-to-date perspective.

Key highlights of this report include:

- **A preliminary analysis of European CIP research and innovation activities**, drawing on the results and classifications of leading EU projects. This analysis is enriched by feedback from over 25 ECSCI projects, providing a thorough snapshot of current capabilities and trends.
- **Initial findings on knowledge and capability gaps** identified through stakeholder consultations. Early insights point to areas where further research and innovation are needed, setting the stage for future strategic initiatives.
- **An outlook on forthcoming value-added reports**, including sector-specific whitepapers and strategic roadmaps. These future publications will delve deeper into CIP challenges, propose targeted solutions, and guide the direction of research and policy development.

This report represents the first step in a continuous process of landscape mapping and strategic analysis. While the current focus is primarily on EU research and innovation projects, future reports will broaden the perspective to include a wider range of activities and stakeholders. Each new edition will bring updated findings, deeper analysis, and practical recommendations to support the ongoing evolution of CIP in Europe.

By regularly publishing these insights, the EU-CIP project aims to empower critical infrastructure operators, solution providers, researchers, and policymakers with the knowledge and foresight needed to address emerging threats and opportunities. The ultimate goal is to foster a more secure, resilient, and innovative critical infrastructure landscape for Europe and beyond.

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Definitions and acronyms

ABM	Agent Based Model
ACS	Access Control System
AFAS	Advanced File Analysis System
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOC	Airport Operation Center
ARM	Advanced RISC Machine
BBTR	Blockchain-based Threat Registry Platform
BDA	Big Data Analytics
BMS	Building Management System
BTMS	Building Threat Monitoring System
CAS	Crisis Alerting System
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CCTV	Closed Circuit TeleVision
CEI	Critical Energy Infrastructures
CEN	Committee for European Norms
CER	Critical Entities Resilience
CG	Capability Gaps
CI	Critical Infrastructure
CIP	Critical Infrastructure Protection
CIR	Critical Infrastructure Resilience
CIPRNet	Critical Infrastructures Preparedness and Resilience Research Network
CIS	Critical Infrastructure Systems
CoP	Communities of Practices
C/P	Cyber/Physical
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSA	Cyber Situation Awareness
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CTI	Cyber Threat Intelligence
DarkNet	Deep and Dark Web Mining and Intelligence
DCS	Data Collection System
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DoA	Description of Action
DSO	Distribution System Operators
DSS	Decision Support System
DT	Digital Twin
DTM	Data Traffic Monitoring
DXL	Data Exchange Layer
EC	European Commission
ECI	European Critical Infrastructure
ECSCI	European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures
EFUS	European Forum for Urban Security
ENTSOE	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity
EPES	Electrical Power and Energy System
EPWS	Emergency Population Warning System

ERNICIP	European Reference Network for Critical Infrastructure Protection
ESORICS	European Symposium on Research in Computer Security
EU	European Union
FAS	Fire Alarm System
FDCE	Forensic Data Collection Engine
GA	Grant Agreement
GIS	Geographical Information System
H2020	Horizon 2020 Framework Programme
HAMS	Hospital Availability Management System
HAS	Hold-up Alarm System
HE	Homomorphic Encryption
HEU	Horizon Europe Framework Programme
ID	Interactive Dashboards
IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IE	Information Element
IFDS	Intrusion and Fire Detection System
IMP	Incident Management Portal
IoT	Internet of Things
IPDSM	impact propagation and decision support model
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
ITTDS	IT Threat Detection System
LIDAR	Laser Radar
LiveNet	Live Security Monitoring and Analysis
LL	Living Labs
MAS	Mobile Alerting System
NIS	Network Information Systems
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NSBs	National Standardization Bodies
OSINT	Open Source Intelligence
OT	Operational Technology
PC	Project Coordinator
PMU	Phasor Measurement Unit
PSA	Physical Situation Awareness
RA	Reference Architecture
RCRA	Real-time Cyber Risk Assessment
RI	Resilience Indicator
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
RTC	Real Time Communications
SA	Situation Awareness
SBDS	Suspicious Behaviour Detection System
SC	Scientific Coordinator
SCI	Smart Critical Infrastructure
SCP	Smart City Platforms
ShareNet	Intelligence and Information Sharing and Dissemination
SEPA	Single Euro Payments Area
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management
SIPS	Sensitive Industrial Plants and Sites

SME	Smart Medium Enterprise
SOC	Security Operation Center
SPA	Security Protocol Analysis
SSO	Single Sign On
SSRI	Strengthening Security Research and Innovation
SWIFT	Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunications
TM	Technical Manager
TRAS	Threat Response and Alert System
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UI	User Interface
VaaS	Vulnerability Assessment as a Service
VDS	Visible Digital Seal
XACML	eXtensible Access Control Markup Language

A network diagram with blue and grey nodes connected by lines, set against a blue geometric background in the top left corner.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the Document

ADVANCING CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE PROTECTION: INSIGHTS AND FORESIGHT FROM THE EU-CIP PROJECT

The security and resilience of Europe’s critical infrastructure are more important than ever in today’s rapidly evolving technological landscape. The EU-CIP project is at the forefront of this effort, dedicated to gathering, analysing, and curating the latest advancements in research, innovation, and technology related to Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP).

WHAT IS THE VALUE OF OUR WORK?

Through the EU-CIP-ANALYSIS pillar, our team systematically maps the current landscape of CIP research and innovation. We go beyond simple information gathering: our approach is designed to identify emerging trends, highlight gaps in knowledge and practice, and provide strategic foresight on future developments. This work directly supports policymakers, industry leaders, and researchers by offering actionable insights and recommendations.

OUR METHODOLOGY: ITERATIVE AND IMPACT-DRIVEN

Our analysis follows a dynamic, iterative methodology. This means we continuously update our findings as new information becomes available, ensuring that our reports reflect the latest developments in the field. Each report in this series builds on previous work, progressively deepening our understanding and providing a clear, evolving picture of the CIP landscape.

WHAT CAN YOU EXPECT FROM OUR REPORTS?

This first value-added report presents initial findings from our extensive desk research, offering a snapshot of the current state of CIP research and innovation. It also outlines our approach for future reports, which will delve deeper into specific topics, technologies, and emerging challenges. Upcoming editions—starting with the next release—will provide even more detailed analysis, foresight, and practical recommendations for stakeholders across Europe.

DELIVERING REAL VALUE

By regularly publishing these value-added reports, the EU-CIP project ensures that its analytical findings are accessible to all interested parties. Our goal is to empower decision-makers, support innovation, and foster collaboration across the critical infrastructure protection community.

1.2. Value-Added Reporting Methodology Overview

The methodology for the production of this and subsequent reports of the series involves the following activities that are also illustrated in the Figure Error. **Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-1:**

- Periodic collection aggregation and consolidation of the findings from different sources. The present report includes information consolidated during the first six months of the project.
- Curation of the findings.
- Foresight analysis of the findings.
- Production of recommendations, roadmaps and other relevant value-added reports such as whitepapers.

Figure Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-1: EU-CIP Analysis Methodology – Findings to be Reported in EU-CIP roadmaps reports

This report carries out a first step towards presenting a comprehensive landscape of CIP/CIR. It reports findings collected based on the following modalities:

A) **Desk research**, including collection of information about Horizon 2020 (H2020)/ Horizon Europe (HEU) projects and their outcomes, with emphasis on projects of the ECSCI cluster.

B) **Stakeholders' Feedback**: As part of this report, EU-CIP has carried out a first round of information collection from stakeholders via the questionnaire that is included as an Annex to this document. Feedback received through this questionnaire is destined to complement the desk research information.

The information collection and analysis based on the above-listed modalities will be updated regularly to reflect changes in the status CIR/CIP landscape. Furthermore, subsequent versions of the report will be complemented with work towards foresight extraction and production of roadmaps. Specifically, the collected information will be analysed to extract foresight knowledge i.e., knowledge on the future of the CIP/CIR evolution, as well as on the

production of roadmaps concerning research activities, technology evolution, as well as standards and policies development.

The methodology for the development of the series of reports includes also the production of value-added reports on capabilities, technologies and CIR/CIP outcomes. Value added reports will focus on:

- A) Aggregated and consolidated view of the capability needs and gaps in CIP/CIR;
- B) Aggregated and consolidated view of the state-of-the-art technologies, techniques, methods and tools that can contribute to fill the identified capability gaps;
- C) Aggregated and consolidated view of outcomes (including on technological, industrial, legal and ethical issues), future trends, lessons learnt, and best practices derived from past and current security research projects. As already outlined, the project will produce additional value-added reports.

The present report exploits information collected from internal stakeholders via questionnaires. The relevant information collection of the report will also serve as a basis for collecting information from external stakeholders, including experts and stakeholders that will join the project. In this respect, the report will facilitate information collection from external stakeholders as part of the project's Type A Open calls.

1.3. Structure of the Report

To help readers navigate and benefit from this report, we have organised the content as follows:

Section 2: Mapping the Landscape

This section presents our initial findings from desk research and consultations with key stakeholders. Here, we provide an overview of current activities and initiatives in Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR) across Europe.

Section 3: Looking Ahead – Foresight and Future Analysis

In this section, we outline the analytical directions and foresight activities planned for future editions of this report. We also introduce some of the main value-added reports that the EU-CIP project will deliver, offering readers a preview of upcoming insights and recommendations.

Section 4: Conclusions and Next Steps

The final section summarises key takeaways and provides an outlook for future editions, highlighting how our ongoing work will continue to deliver value to the CIP/CIR community.

Annexes

To support transparency and further exploration, we include several annexes:

Annex I: The template used to gather landscape information from internal stakeholders.

Annex II: The feedback form designed for internal stakeholder input.

Annex III: A curated list of EU projects focused on CIP/CIR, each with a brief description and a link to its website.

Annex IV: A compilation of relevant ISO standards for risk management in CIP/CIR.

This structure is designed to provide both a comprehensive overview and practical resources for all interested stakeholders.

2. The Landscape of CIP/CIR Solutions

2.1. Landscape Anatomy

This section reviews R&I projects and initiatives, scientific findings, standards and information collected from EU-CIP partners. The analysis of the collected information is done along the line of technologies, standards and policies. Annex I includes the “Information Collection Form” and “Internal Stakeholders Feedback Form”, which was developed in the project and provided to (project) internal and external experts.

It is important to note that this report represents a snapshot of ongoing work. As the EU-CIP project progresses, we will continue to update and expand our findings.

2.2. Landscape of CIP R&I Initiatives

The Framework Programmes for Research and Technological Development, also called Framework Programmes (abbreviated FP1 to FP9), provide the landscape where CIP and CIR projects are typically situated. The FP are funding programmes created by the European Union/European Commission to support and foster research in the European Research Area (ERA). The funding programmes began in 1984 and continue to the present day. Specific objectives and actions vary between funding periods. Horizon 2020 already had dedicated budgets for CIP and CIR projects, which were mainly located in the “societal challenges” pillar in the societal challenge 7 “secure societies”.

The current set up of the Framework Programme (Horizon Europe) is shown in Figure **Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-2**. The CIP and CIR related projects under concern for this evaluation are residing in the civil security for society cluster (cluster 3 of pillar 2).

This pillar supports research relating to societal challenges and reinforces technological and industrial capacities through clusters. It sets ambitious goals for EU missions. It also includes the Joint Research Centre which supports EU and national policymakers with independent scientific evidence and technical support.

Figure *Errore*. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-2: Localisation of CIP/CIR Projects (source: <https://www.horizon-eu.eu/>)

EU-CIP will establish an easily accessible overview of those projects, which have been funded in the course of European research in the area of critical infrastructures. This mainly focuses on the projects funded amongst the destination “resilient infrastructure” under cluster 3 of Horizon Europe and on the “societal challenges” pillar in the societal challenge 7 “secure societies” of Horizon 2020.

2.2.1. The Landscape of EU Projects on CIP

2.2.1.1. Overview

The infrastructure (INFRA) and the Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) projects of H2020 are dedicated to the cyber-physical security for protecting critical infrastructures that support finance, energy, health, air transport, communication, gas, and water. Furthermore, there are other security projects (e.g., cyber-security related projects) that include technologies and use cases focused on the protection of critical infrastructures. The secure operation of these critical infrastructures is essential to the security of a nation, its economy, and the public's health and safety. Security incidents in the critical infrastructures can directly lead to a violation of users' safety and privacy, physical damages, significant economic impacts on individuals and companies, and threats to human life while decreasing trust in institutions and questioning their social value. Because of the increasing interconnection between the digital and physical worlds, these infrastructures and services are more critical, sophisticated and interconnected than ever before. This makes them increasingly vulnerable to attacks, as confirmed by the steady rise of cyber-security incidents, such as phishing or ransomware, but also cyber-physical incidents, such as physical violation of devices or facilities in conjunction with malicious cyber activities.

Most of the INFRA and CIP projects are clustered around The European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures (ECSCI - <https://www.finsec-project.eu/ecsci>) with the driving force to create synergies and foster emerging disruptive solutions to security issues via cross-project collaboration and innovation. Table *Errore*. Nel documento non esiste testo

dello stile specificato.-1 lists the ECSCI member projects (as of February 2023). Furthermore, a high-level description of the considered projects based on their websites and their overview on CORDIS is provided in Appendix II.

Table Error!. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-1: EU funded projects and their websites

#	Project Name	Project Title	GA No.	Website
1	ANASTACIA	Advanced Networked Agents for Security and Trust Assessment in CPS / IOT Architectures	731558	http://www.anastacia-h2020.eu/
2	ATLANTIS	Improved resilience of Critical Infrastructures Against Large scale transNational and systemic risks	101073909	https://www.atlantis-horizon.eu/
3	CyberSANE	Cyber Security Incident Handling, Warning and Response System for the European Critical Infrastructures	833683	https://www.cybersane-project.eu/
4	CyberSEAS	Cyber Securing Energy data Services	101020560	https://cyberseas.eu/
5	DEFENDER	Defending the European Energy Infrastructures	740898	https://defender-project.eu/
6	EnergyShield	Integrated Cybersecurity Solution for the Vulnerability Assessment, Monitoring and Protection of Critical Energy Infrastructures	832907	https://energy-shield.eu/
7	ENSURESEC	End-to-end Security of the Digital Single Market's E-commerce and Delivery Service Ecosystem	883242	http://www.ensuresec.eu/
8	EU-HYBNET	Empowering a Pan-European Network to Counter Hybrid Threats	883054	https://euhybnet.eu/
9	FeatureCloud	Privacy preserving federated machine learning and blockchaining for reduced	826078	https://featurecloud.eu/

#	Project Name	Project Title	GA No.	Website
		cyber risks in a world of distributed healthcare		
10	FINSEC	Integrated Framework for Predictive and Collaborative Security of Financial Infrastructures	786727	https://www.finsec-project.eu
11	IMPETUS	Intelligent Management of Processes, Ethics and Technology for Urban Safety	883286	https://www.impetus-project.eu/
12	InfraStress	Improving resilience of sensitive industrial plants & infrastructures exposed to cyber-physical threats, by means of an open testbed stress-testing system	833088	https://www.infrastress.eu/
13	PHOENIX	Electrical Power System's Shield against complex incidents and extensive cyber and privacy attacks	832989	https://phoenix-h2020.eu/
14	PRAETORIAN	Protection of Critical Infrastructures from advanced combined cyber and physical threats	101021274	https://praetorian-h2020.eu/
15	PRECINCT	Preparedness and Resilience Enforcement for Critical INfrastructure Cascading Cyberphysical Threats and effects with focus on district or regional protection	101021668	https://www.precinct.info/en/
16	RESISTO	RESilience enhancement and risk control platform for communication infraSTRUCTure Operators	786409	http://www.resisto-project.eu/
17	SAFECARE	SAFEguard of Critical heAlth infrastructure	787002	https://www.safecare-project.eu/
18	SAFETY4RAILS	Data-based analysis for SAFETY and security protection FOR detection,	883532	https://safety4rails.eu/

#	Project Name	Project Title	GA No.	Website
		prevention, mitigation and response in trans-modal metro and RAILway networkS		
19	SATIE	Security of Air Transport Infrastructure of Europe	832969	http://satie-h2020.eu
20	SAURON	Scalable multidimensional situation awareness solution for protecting European ports	740477	http://sauronproject.eu
21	SealedGRID	Scalable, trusted, and interoperable platform for secured smart GRID	777996	https://www.sgrid.eu/
22	SecureGas	Securing The European Gas Network	833017	https://www.securegas-project.eu/
23	SmartResilience	Smart Resilience Indicators for Smart Critical Infrastructures	700621	http://www.smartresilience.eu-vri.eu/
24	SOTER	cyberSecurity Optimization and Training for Enhanced Resilience in finance	833923	https://soterproject.eu/
25	SPHINX	A Universal Cyber Security Toolkit for Health-Care Industry	826183	https://sphinx-project.eu/
26	STOP-IT	Strategic, Tactical, Operational Protection of water Infrastructure against cyber-physical Threats	740610	https://stop-it-project.eu/
27	SUNRISE	Sustainable Urban Neighbourhoods - Research and Implementation Support in Europe	101073821	https://sunrise-europe.eu/
28	7SHIELD	Safety and Security Standards of Space Systems, ground Segments and Satellite data assets, via	883284	https://www.7shield.eu/

#	Project Name	Project Title	GA No.	Website
		prevention, detection, response and mitigation of physical and cyber threats		
29	PANOPTIS	Development of a Decision Support System for increasing the Resilience of Transportation Infrastructure based on combined use of terrestrial and airborne sensors and advanced modelling tools	769129	http://www.panoptis.eu/
30	CONCORDIA	Cyber security cOmpeteNCe fOr Research and InnovAtion	830927	https://www.concordia-h2020.eu/
31	Digital-Water.City	DIGITAL-WATER.city - Leading urban water management to its digital future	820954	http://www.digital-water.city/
32	DYNABIC	Dynamic business continuity and response of critical systems against advanced cyber-physical threats	101070455	https://dynabic.eu/

2.2.1.2. Categorisation of EU-funded Projects on Sectors

The projects have developed and deployed novel techniques for integrated security modelling, IoT security, artificial intelligence for securing critical infrastructures, resilience of critical infrastructures, ethical and legal aspects of cybersecurity, combating hybrid threats to critical infrastructure, cyber and physical threats detection, increased automation for detection, prevention and mitigation measures, information and knowledge sharing, standards and regulations for the protection of critical infrastructures, common platforms for cascading effects on the different critical infrastructures, combined safety and security solutions, cyber security awareness, and the landscape of advanced combined cyber and physical threats. All these techniques have been presented in the ECSCI workshop series (1st and 2nd). Moreover, the projects address CIP solutions and use cases in a variety of different sectors as illustrated in Table Errore. **Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile**

¹ <https://www.steinbeis-edition.de/shop/out/pictures/media/218957.pdf>

² <https://www.steinbeis-edition.de/shop/out/pictures/media/9783956632853.pdf>

specificato.-2 and cover different technologies as illustrated in Table **Errore.** **Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-3.**

*Table **Errore.** Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-2: EU funded projects vs. sectors*

Project	Transport	Communication	Energy	Finance	Gas	Healthcare	Industry	Smart Resilience	Water	Sector Agnostic
ANASTACIA										X
ATLANTIS			X							
CONCORDIA										X
CyberSANE										X
CyberSEAS			X							
DEFENDER			X							
Digital-Water.City									X	
EnergyShield			X							
ENSURESEC				X						
EU-HYBNET										X
FeatureCloud		X								
FINSEC				X						
IMPETUS										X
InfraStress							X			
PANOPTIS	X									
PHOENIX			X							
PRAETORIAN										X
PRECINCT										X
RESISTO		X								
SAFECARE						X				
SAFETY4RAILS										
SATIE	X									
SAURON		X								
SealedGRID			X							

Project	Transport	Communication	Energy	Finance	Gas	Healthcare	Industry	Smart Resilience	Water	Sector Agnostic
SecureGas					X					
SmartResilience								X		
SOTER				X						
SPHINX						X				
STOP-IT									X	
SUNRISE		X								
7SHIELD		X								
DYNABIC										X

Table *Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.*-3: Projects vs Technologies

Project	Alert and Response systems	Anomaly Detection	Blockchain/DLT Technology	Detection of cyber threats	Detection of physical threats	Decision support systems	Disinformation Management	Global Situation Awareness	Modelling cascading effects	Predictive analytics	Risk Management	SIEM	Others
ANASTACIA				X	X								
ATLANTIS								X			X		
CONCORDIA				X									X
CyberSANE				X						X			
CyberSEAS				X	X			X			X		
DEFENDER				X	X								
Digital-Water.City	X					X				X			
DYNABIC				X	X						X		
EnergyShield		X						X				X	
ENSURESEC	X							X					
EU-HYBNET				X			X	X					

Project	Alert and Response systems	Anomaly Detection	Blockchain/ DLT Technology	Detection of cyber threats	Detection of physical threats	Decision support systems	Disinformation Management	Global Situation Awareness	Modelling cascading effects	Predictive analytics	Risk Management	SIEM	Others
FeatureCloud		X	X	X									
FINSEC	X	X	X	X	X					X	X	X	
IMPETUS	X			X	X								
InfraStress	X			X	X			X			X		
PANOPTIS						X					X		
PHOENIX	X			X					X		X		
PRAETORIAN	X			X	X			X			X		
PRECINCT				X	X				X			X	
RESISTO	X			X	X	X		X			X		
SAFECARE	X	X		X	X						X		
SAFETY4RAILS	X			X	X	X				X	X		
SATIE	X			X	X			X			X		
SAURON				X	X			X					
SealedGRID			X	X	X						X		
SecureGas				X	X								X
SmartResilience									X		X		X
SOTER	X		X	X				X					
SPHINX	X			X		X							
STOP-IT	X	X		X	X	X			X		X	X	
SUNRISE								X	X		X		
7SHIELD	X			X	X			X			X		

2.2.2. Clusters and Other Initiatives

2.2.2.1. European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures (ECSCI)

Overview

The European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures (ECSCI - <https://www.finsec-project.eu/ecsci>) is a cluster of EU funded running projects and ended projects (the latter still represented by their former coordinators) as illustrated in Figure Errore. **Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-3. ECSCI was founded in the beginning of 2020 and is continuously attracting more members. The establishment of the cluster was initiated from industrial and research partners of CIP related projects, without being a contractual obligation of any of the projects. Its main objective is to create synergies and foster emerging disruptive solutions to security issues to protect critical infrastructures and services via cross-project collaboration and innovation. To promote its activities, ECSCI organizes international conferences, and national or international workshops, involving both policy makers, industry and academic, practitioners, and representatives from the European Commission.

Figure Errore. **Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-3: Overview of the ECSCI cluster

The ECSCI cluster shares experiences and best practices about CIP in different sectors, consolidates and reflects a European approach for cyber-physical and hybrid threat intelligence in the CIP domain, and focuses on research that protects and secures critical infrastructures and services respecting the differences between individual projects, such as the different approaches, the sectors of interest, or target groups, while establishing tight and productive connections with closely related or complementary H2020 and HEU projects. Members of the cluster engage in various activities:

- (i) Scientific collaborations, in the form of joint workshops and conferences, co-writing of academic publications,
- (ii) Technical collaborations, such as sharing approaches on cyber-physical security, risk assessment, and predictive analytics,

- (iii) Communication and dissemination of information about the cluster's activities and outputs through common web and social media presence as well as joint events,
- (iv) Building and fostering stakeholders' alliances, allowing for the mobilisation of local ecosystems, and
- (v) Marketplace extensions of members and their products/services across various sectors. Figure Errore. **Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-3 shows the 30 ECSCI member projects (as of April 2023) and collaboration activities.

Publications, Proceedings, Newsletters and other Scientific Results of the Cluster

The ECSCI cluster members co-edited two Open Access Books and contributed to book chapters:

1. [Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence for Critical Infrastructures Security: A Guide to Integrated Cyber-Physical Protection of Modern Critical Infrastructures](#)
2. [Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence for Critical Infrastructures Security: Securing Critical Infrastructures in Air Transport, Water, Gas, Healthcare, Finance and Industry](#)

They also contributed to the following Proceedings and Newsletters:

- [Consolidated Proceedings of the 1st ECSCI Workshop on Critical Infrastructure Protection](#) based on the [1st ECSCI Virtual Workshop](#), held online on the 24th-25th of June 2020
- [Consolidated Proceedings of the 2nd ECSCI Workshop on Critical Infrastructure Protection](#) based on the [2nd ECSCI Virtual Workshop](#), held online on the 27th-29th of April 2022
- [Computer Security. ESORICS 2021 International Workshops: CyberICPS, SECPRE, ADIoT, SPOSE, CPS4CIP, and CDT&SECOMANE](#)
- [Cyber-Physical Security for Critical Infrastructures Protection](#)
- [Computer Security: ESORICS 2019 International Workshops, IOSec, MSTEC, and FINSEC](#)
- [Computer Security. ESORICS 2022 International Workshops: CDT&SECOMANE, CPS4CIP, CyberICPS, EIS, SecAssure, SECPRE, and SPOSE, Copenhagen, Denmark, September 26-30, 2022](#)
- Two articles in the [Newsletter on Critical Infrastructure Resilience](#):
 - [The European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures \(ECSCI\)](#)
 - [Report on the 2nd ECSCI Workshop on Critical Infrastructure Protection](#)

The cluster members have also collaborated in the organization of scientific Workshops such as the CPS4CIP Workshop series that is co-located with the well-established European Symposium on Research in Computer Security (ESORICS) series of conferences. Specifically, the cluster has had a leading role in the organization of the following workshops:

- [FINSEC 2019: 1st International Workshop on Security for Financial Critical Infrastructures and Services](#) Co-located with [ESORICS 2019](#)
- [CPS4CIP 2020: The 1st International Workshop on Cyber-Physical Security for Critical Infrastructures Protection](#) Co-located with [ESORICS 2020](#)

- [CPS4CIP 2021: The 2nd International Workshop on Cyber-Physical Security for Critical Infrastructures Protection](#) Co-located with [ESORICS 2021](#)
- [CPS4CIP 2022: The 3rd International Workshop on Cyber-Physical Security for Critical Infrastructures Protection](#) Co-located with [ESORICS 2022](#)

Events, Journals and Websites Related to CIP/CIR

The following web sites relate to the ECSCI cluster activities on CIP. Some of them have recently referenced the clusters and its results.

- 2E!SAC Association for Improving Vital Infrastructure Resilience in Europe (<https://2eisacresiliencetool.eu-vri.eu/>)
- ASIS Europe (<https://asiseurope.org/>).
- BEYOND Expo (<https://www.beyond-expo.gr/>).
- Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience Europe Expo (<https://www.cipre-expo.com/>).
- CIPRNet (Critical Infrastructures Preparedness and Resilience Research Network) (<https://ciprnet.eu/>).
- CyberWatching.eu (<https://cyberwatching.eu/>), the portal for cybersecurity and Privacy research results for a resilient Europe.
- CyberSecPro: Market Need and Demand (<https://cybersecpro-project.eu>).
- ENTSO-E Vision: A Power System for a Carbon Neutral Europe (<https://www.entsoe.eu/>).
- European Reference Network for Critical Infrastructure Protection (ERNICIP) (<https://erncip-project.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>).
- European Network of Transmission System Operators for Gas (<https://www.entsog.eu/>).
- Europe's Distribution System Operators (DSOs) (<https://www.edsoforsmartgrids.eu/>).
- European Forum for Urban Security (<https://efus.eu/>).
- FINSEC Marketplace (<https://finsecurity.eu/>), which includes information about solutions and knowledge developed in the cluster's project.
- Gas Infrastructure Europe (<https://www.gie.eu/>)
- Global Infrastructure Hub (<https://infrachallenge.github.org/podcast/>)
- International Association of CIP professionals (<https://cip-association.org/>).
- International Journal of Critical Infrastructures, <https://www.inderscience.com/jhome.php?jcode=ijcis>
- International Journal of Information Security, <https://www.springer.com/journal/10207>
- Italian node of the European Infrastructure Simulation and Analysis Centre (<http://www.eisac.it/>)
- Journal of Critical Infrastructure Policy, <https://www.jcip1.org/>

- ScienceDirect International Journal of Critical Infrastructure Protection (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/international-journal-of-critical-infrastructure-protection>)
- SINAPSE - **free public service** of the European Commission, which has hosted articles and news about the cluster.

2.2.2.2. Community for European Research and Innovation Security (CERIS)

The CERIS community³ has been established by the European Commission (EC). It is a community of users in the security domain. CERIS brings together academia, research institutes, public authorities, and industry practitioners. It fosters the collaboration of these stakeholders towards building disaster resilient societies with more effective border management and better measurements to fight crime and terrorism. In this direction, the community is participating in a series of events that are organized by the European Commission and its Directorate-General like DG HOME, respectively. CERIS is not directly addressing critical infrastructures. Nevertheless, several of its security and border control technologies can be applied in the area of critical infrastructure resilience as well.

2.3. Scientific State of the Art: A Brief Overview

Critical Infrastructures (CIs) play an important role in safeguarding a country's societal well-being and economy. CIs are vital sources for operating different applications and require much attention concerning their safety, security and resilience (e.g., [1], [2]). Some of the most common sectors of CIs in different countries include energy, transportation, and water management. The use of Operational Technology (OT) in CIs has increased over the recent years, which has various benefits like improving the operational efficiency of CIs. However, this also introduces additional vulnerabilities to potential cyber-attacks and expands the attack surface in CIs. It is crucial to ensure the resilience of CIs, which are paramount for economic development and day-to-day requirements but are threatened by intentional threats. Therefore, CI protection (CIP) prior and restoration after intentional attacks are significant [1].

Masi et al. [3] developed a Digital Twin (DT) architecture for CIP. The developed approach continuously collects security-related information such as vulnerabilities, security threats from the IoT devices of critical sectors in the physical world and integrates updates from the virtual world. It allows analytics, prediction and anticipation of cyber threats by performing simulation and experimentation virtually, and responses of prevention measures autonomously to the physical world. The authors have implemented their approach on two real-world use cases a) a cooperative transport system and b) a road tunnel scenario. Kevin et al. [4] developed a methodology that intersects two domains, including deep learning (DL) and CIP, by illustrating how DL can help offer resilient solutions for the electricity sector. DL mainly focus on the performance of DL models and their accuracy, but they often overlook the accountability and trustworthiness of the models' decisions. Thus, DL for CIP

³ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/ceris-community-european-research-and-innovation-security_en

must allow transparent and understandable security decision-making procedures pushing the methods accountable for automatic measures.

Red et al. [5] elaborated on critical infrastructure resilience (CIR) in terms of how it could be integrated into the current safety and security practices based on ISO 31000 risk management standards. Risk management is critical in dealing with both intentional (security-related) and unintentional (safety-related) threats. From CIR management framework perspective, risk assessment is an essential phase of the risk management process because it serves as the foundation for risk treatment decisions.

Galbusera, et al. [6] presented a game-based training concept in critical infrastructure protection and resilience (CIPR). In the CIPR domain, game-based training and exercises increase awareness and offer suitable computer-based training solutions. Gromek [7] presented strategic TEs for CIPR, which include the transition from lessons learned to effective curricula. Strategic TEs for CIPR are notably dedicated to experienced practitioners who can utilise their learning and understanding to holistically solve complex CIPR problems by implementing decision-making theory and tools.

Eid [8] argued that an effective assessment of the CI's resilience and preparedness requires real coupled models of threats dynamic and developed some basic ideas about coupled modelling using stochastic modelling approach to coupling the dynamics of the threat with that of the CIs.

Pursiainen and Kytömaa [9] conducted a public policy analysis of the development of legislation on critical infrastructure in the European Union (EU), highlighting its change, promises and challenges and concluded that that the new CER Directive attests to increasing regulation of the CI sector, both broadening and deepening the supranational tendencies in this field.

The changing threat landscape with fast-moving developments such as cyber threats, geopolitical developments, and technological innovation, makes it necessary to study the gaps and research needs for the assessment and protection of critical infrastructures to enhance their resilience against evolving and extreme threats. To securely manage critical infrastructures, it is argued that to identify all threats and risks that pose greatest risks to critical infrastructures rather than focusing on one type of threat at a time using risk assessment methods, environmental risk mitigation strategies, and human factor in the prevention of risks [10]. To properly govern critical infrastructure resilience, it is argued to employ the performance-based and attribute-based approaches for resilience assessment of critical infrastructure resilience [11]. As recent COVID-19 has shown that most critical infrastructure systems (CISs) cannot stand against all potential disruptions there is a need for a transition from robust design to resilience design of CISs, increasing the focus on preparedness, response, and recovery [12]. Based on their literature review, the authors conclude that CIS can be considered resilient if it possesses the following capabilities:

- (i) the ability to imagine what to expect,
- (ii) the ability to protect and resist a disruption,
- (iii) the ability to absorb the adverse effects of disruption,
- (iv) the ability to adapt to new conditions and changes caused by disruption, and
- (v) the ability to recover its normal performance level after a disruption.

The recent analysis of critical infrastructure dependencies before and since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic has revealed changes in the focus on critical infrastructures and in the

perception of what makes critical infrastructures critical [13]. The authors argue that a shift of focus from the sectors of energy, water, transport & traffic, and ICT before the start of the COVID-19 pandemic was happened to the sectors public health, constitutional institutions, transport & traffic, and food since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic. Further they argue that infrastructures which had previously not been classified as critical being discussed as new critical infrastructures, e.g., “urban green spaces to be essential for the health and well-being of citizens during lockdown times, and social services like childcare, care of the elderly, delivery services, and online grocery shopping have been highlighted as essential services for maintaining workforces and the functioning of society during a pandemic”.

To bridge the gap between cybersecurity and reliability of critical infrastructures some authors introduced a new research area under the broad term of securability to discuss new methodologies that could map better the system requirements by incorporating security (and privacy) with reliability (and safety) [14]. Although cybersecurity training for CIP is available across educational types and levels there is a general agreement on best measures and methods for cybersecurity training has yet to be reached [15]. Authors seek to establish the current state-of-the-art in cyber-security training offerings for CIP and the key performance indicators that allow evaluating their effectiveness and their analysis results “show that solutions that provide hands-on experience, team skills development, high level of real-life fidelity are often preferred to other options, with simulation-based solutions showing the highest amount of research and development”.

In [16] the different approaches to security in several different industrial sectors (e.g., finance, healthcare, energy, transport, communications, water) were presented. The peculiarities of critical infrastructure protection in each one of these sectors have been discussed and addressed by the different projects of the ECSCI cluster that presented their outcomes, discussing the technical, ethical and societal aspects and the underlying technologies (related to security modelling, IoT security, artificial intelligence, combating hybrid threats, increased automation for threats detection, prevention and mitigation measures, information and knowledge sharing, etc.).

When it comes to combating hybrid threats, the response to the constantly changing and evolving Hybrid threats (asymmetry and unexpectedness) needs to be constantly evolving to keep up. While Bajarūnas [17] argues that addressing hybrid threats is a constant, never-ending process that requires the development of societal and governmental resilience, Vaseashta [18] posits an approach for a multisectoral, multidisciplinary, local, state and whole-of-government systems that conjoins hybrid threats to its social, infrastructural and informational dependencies.

Note that the members of the ECSCI clusters have significant scientific contributions in the above areas. These contributions

ECSCI’s contributions to proceedings:

[ESORICS 2022 Workshops \(ADIoT, CDT&SECOMANE, CPS4CIP, CyberICPS, EIS, SecAssure, SECPRE, SP-MIoT, SPOSE\) \(under publication\) 2022](#). The ECSCI supported CPS4CIP workshop contributed with ten accepted articles which represented an interesting mix of techniques for resilience, cyber-physical threats, risk assessment and emergency response, secure communications, honeypot management, reverse engineering, hardware tracing, cyber-physical systems security, standards, and ICS Datasets.

[Computer Security. ESORICS 2021 International Workshops: CyberICPS, SECPRE, ADIoT, SPOSE, CPS4CIP, and CDT&SECOMANE](#). The ECSCI supported CPS4CIP contributed with

four accepted articles which represented an interesting mix of techniques for resilience, security threat, vulnerability, and malware detection.

[Cyber-Physical Security for Critical Infrastructures Protection 2020](#). The ECSCI supported CPS4CIP workshop contributed with fourteen accepted articles which represented an interesting mix of techniques for the security threat intelligence, data anomaly detection (predict and prevent), computer vision and dataset for security, security management and governance, and impact propagation and power traffic analysis.

[Computer Security: ESORICS 2019 International Workshops, IOSec, MSTEC, and FINSEC](#). The ECSCI supported FINSEC workshop contributed with four accepted articles which represented an interesting mix of techniques for the identification, mitigation, security information sharing, and threats mapping in critical financial infrastructure and services.

2.4. Preliminary Market and State of Practice Analysis

2.4.1. CIP/CIR Measures and Systems

Providing security is one of the central concerns of any society. There is no policy area without a crucial component of security. A safe and secure environment is the very basis on which any stable society is founded upon. A competitive EU based security industry offering solutions for enhanced security can make a substantial contribution to the resilience of European society⁴.

According to a “Study on the Competitiveness on the EU security industry” performed by Ecorys Research and Consulting on the EU security industry on behalf of the European Commission, a general distinction between two different security threat categories has been performed:

- **Traditional security**, corresponding to protection against (‘endogenous’) threats such as ‘ordinary’ criminal activity, fire protection, etc.
- **New security** corresponds to protection against (‘exogenous’) threats such as terrorism, organised crime, cyber-crime, etc. and also including protection against and response to major catastrophic events⁵.

⁴ Communication from the commission to the European parliament, the council and the European economic and social committee. Security Industrial Policy Action Plan for an innovative and competitive Security Industry. (2012). 233 final. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:52012DC0417:EN:NOT>

⁵ ECORYS. (2009). Study on the Competitiveness of the EU security industry Within the Framework Contract for Sectoral Competitiveness Studies –ENTR/06/054 Final Report Client: Directorate-General Enterprise & Industry Brussels, 15 November 2009. www.decision.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/Study-on-the-Competitiveness-of-the-EU-security-industry.pdf

It is necessary to deal with the CIP issues as a complex system because with critical infrastructure protection (as well as with security in general) it applies that a system is as strong as its weakest link. This means that the individual measures for CIP (the ways of protecting the CI) must be balanced, intertwined and complementary. A risk and crisis management approach constitute a systematic process to manage risk and it is fundamental to incorporate it in the daily strategy. Nowadays, every society is exposed to a great amount of a variety of risks and threats, dealing with IT security is an imperative, the measures for critical infrastructure protection are based on a complex approach to security that includes both risk management and physical protection actions. The basic measures for CI protection are:

- **Risk and crisis management:** A risk and crisis management approach constitutes a systematic process to manage risk and it is fundamental to incorporate it in the daily strategy. The strategy consists of five phases representing the necessary scope of process-based risk and crisis management. The five phases are:
 1. Preliminary planning to establish a system of risk and crisis management.
 2. Risk analysis (Assessment, Evaluation, Treatment).
 3. Specification of preventive measures.
 4. Implementation of a crisis management system.
 5. Regular evaluation of the previous phases.
- **Business continuity planning:** defined as a series of activities focused on decreasing the risk of collision emergence and restricting impacts on critical processes. It is not only a plan of a response to a critical event but also includes an important aspect of prevention.
- **IT Security:** the main elements/parts of the IT security are to set up a set of rules and requirements to ensure the protection and security of information and IT/OT architectures; management of physical access and authorization to ensure that only the personnel could access to critical information; set up an authentication and authorization process; a Security supervision, monitoring and management system; implementing antivirus solutions and protection for the web (firewall, IDS/IPS sensor, content filters, antispam and antivirus protection); adopt a data encryption system; and protecting mobile devices.
- **Physical protection** of any object (building, appliance, object etc.) is achieved by combining and intertwining of three basic elements: physical protection systems, response team/activity, regime protection.
 - Physical protection systems that include:
 - Mechanical barrier systems in object concepts as the building are walls, roofs, floors, doors and windows objects. Generally, these are for example: safety locks, grilles, security film, security and toughened laminated glass, safe, safety deposit boxes.
 - Technical protection systems are: Intruder and/or Hold-up Alarm System (HAS); Security Camera System (CCTV system, CCTV surveillance system); Fire alarm system (FAS); Access Control System (ACS); Mechatronics System.
 - Response team/activity: carried out by own resources, security, private security service employees or by police or army. The core is a response of a human element to danger/security disruption/object protection such as breaking in, technological breakdown etc.
 - Regime protection/measure: administrative and organization measures for securing protected interests and values. This includes checking the entrance of employees,

clients, visitors; property protection against theft, damage; continuity and security of operation.

- **Personal and administrative security** intended as the determination and subsequent documentation of security roles and responsibilities according to requirements of the company security policy. In order to ensure an adequate level of security, it is necessary to carry out inspections with the new employees⁶.

For a classification of the security products, the Ecorys report on Security Regulation, Conformity Assessment & Certification⁷, classifies security products into two main categories, depending on familiarity of operation and function:

- **General purpose security products (Type-1):** security products and solutions aimed at addressing ‘familiar’ security situations (security threats or functions) through the application of improved but existing technology. This includes what may loosely be called ‘traditional’ security equipment (e.g. intruder detection, CCTV, access control, security barriers).
- **Priority and sensitive security products (Type-2):** security products and solutions addressing ‘unfamiliar’ or new types of threats that often require the development or application of new technologies and approaches. This latter category may be extended to changes in organisation and implementation of security functions; for example, through the automatization of security functions. This includes what may loosely be called ‘new’ security equipment (i.e., corresponding to products/technologies developed primarily to address threats such as terrorism, organised crime, cyber-crime, etc.).

In general, critical infrastructure protection methodologies, models and simulations are used to understand infrastructure systems, their interdependencies, vulnerabilities, impacts of potential failures and their propagation across interdependent infrastructure systems, based on risk assessments of all the involved critical infrastructures. They may also be used to support performance measurement, conceptual design, impact evaluation, response planning, vulnerability analyses and economic impact assessments.

Another classification of critical infrastructure protection tools is based on their purpose, namely their functionality as follow:

- Risk identification.
- Risk assessment.
- Risk prioritization.
- Risk mitigation planning.
- Effectiveness evaluation.

This approach follows risk assessment purposes, so it is also linked to the fundamental role of risk management.

⁶ Ludek, L., Necesal, L. International journal of mathematical models and methods in applied sciences Issue 7, Volume 5, 20111249 Measures for Critical infrastructure protection

⁷ ECORYS. (2011). Security Regulation, Conformity Assessment & Certification Final Report – Volume I: Main Report Client: European Commission DG Enterprise and Industry Brussels, October 2011. <http://www.decision.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/Security-Regulation-Conformity-Assessment-Certification.pdf>

According to the National Infrastructure Protection Plan (NIPP)⁸, tools, frameworks, and methodologies are classified according to the purpose that they serve, i.e., the stage of the risk management framework that they aid with their output. In Figure **Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-4, the classification of the 68 tools according to the risk management purpose is shown. This represents a review of the capabilities of various not only strategies and applications, but also methodologies which are used for both identification and evaluation or risks that occur in critical infrastructure. Tools that lie deeper than others in the same branch support additional risk analysis purposes⁹.

There is not a unique approach to protect critical infrastructures, but there is always great necessity of interdependencies analysis in order to understand the interconnections which exist between multiple critical infrastructures.

⁸ <https://www.cisa.gov/national-infrastructure-protection-plan>

⁹ Stergiopoulos, G., Vasilellis, E., Lykou, G., Kotzanikolaou, P., Gritzalis, D. (2016). Classification and Comparison of Critical Infrastructure Protection Tools. 10th International Conference on Critical Infrastructure Protection (ICCIP), Mar 2016, Arlington, VA, United States. pp.239-255, 10.1007/978-3-319-48737-3_14. hal-01614869

Figure **Errore**. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-4: CIP tools classification according to risk management purpose

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

2.4.2. Existing EU projects' CIP/CIR measures and systems

2.4.2.1. Overview

The EU programmes¹⁰ have funded over 100 critical infrastructure protection projects from 2007 onwards, including several of the project outlined earlier (e.g., the projects of the ECSCI cluster). These projects focused on a variety of issues including national and European information sharing and alerting systems, the development of ways to assess interdependence between electronic and electricity transmission networks, and the creation of a 'good practice' manual for policy makers. The EU programme is designed to protect citizens and critical infrastructures from terrorist attacks and other security incidents by fostering prevention and preparedness, namely by improving the protection of critical infrastructures and addressing crisis management. A Europe-wide approach helps manage the risks across the EU. Reducing the vulnerabilities of critical infrastructure and increasing their resilience is one of the major objectives of the EU. An adequate level of protection must be ensured and the detrimental effects of disruptions on the society and citizens must be limited as far as possible. EU-funded security projects will be reviewed with the aim of examining current attempts at categorisations of CIP measures, products and systems in order to provide building blocks for the EU-CIP project, and also to gather information on available security technologies and the needs that they help address. The CIR/CIP measures and systems will be expanded in future reports.

2.4.2.2. SAURON Project

SAURON¹¹ project - Scalable multidimensional situational awareness solution for protecting European ports - , funded under H2020 programme, addresses the topic CIP-01-2016-2017 (From 01/05/2017 to 30/04/2020) and puts the focus on protection of EU Ports under Transport Infrastructure and means of transportation type of CI. Security threats in ports increasingly come not only in physical form but also as cyber-attacks on critical communications systems. SAURON project proposes the holistic situation awareness concept as an integrated, scalable and yet installation-specific solution for protecting EU ports and its surroundings. The vision of SAURON is to provide a multidimensional yet installation-specific Situational Awareness (SA) platform to help port operators anticipate and withstand potential cyber, physical or combined threats to their freight and cargo business and to the safety of their employees, visitors, passengers and citizens in the vicinity.

SAURON solution combines the more advanced physical security features with the newest techniques in prevention, detection and mitigation of cyber-threats, including synthetic cyberspace aspects through the use of new visualization techniques such as immersive interfaces and cyber 3D models. In addition, a Hybrid Situation Awareness (HSA) application capable of determining the potential consequences of any threat shows the potential cascading effect of a detected threat both in the physical and cyber domains. SAURON can be used to engage with the public in surrounding areas and rescue/security teams that will be able to communicate any potential event or situation that could put their safety at risk. Reducing the vulnerabilities of EU ports, as one of the main European critical

¹⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/pages/page/critical-infrastructure_en

¹¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/740477/it>

infrastructures and increasing their systemic resilience in the face of a physical, cyber or combined threat is also part of the SAURON main objective. Table *Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.*-4 shows the main tools of SAURON.

Table Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-4: SAURON project's main tools

Focus: protection of EU Ports under Transport Infrastructure and means of transportation type of CI.	
Detection of physical and cyber threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A complete physical SA (PSA) system which includes novel features such as dynamic location of resources and assets, location, management and monitoring of sensors, including cameras mounted on drones, security perimeter control, robust and secure tactical communication network and so on. • An advanced and scalable cyber SA (CSA) system capable of preventing and detecting threats and in case of a declared attack, capable of mitigating the effects of the infection/intrusion. This CSA system will include new visualization paradigms for the cyber space. • The SAURON CSA application relies on a cyber-security monitoring platform that will be able to acquire, process and analyse information gathered from multiple sources. • On a real-time basis, different cyber security sensors are gathering the relevant information from these sources, processing the data in different cyber security incident detectors and sending possible incidents to a correlation engine.
Correlation engine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A correlation engine processes all the collected information and applies intelligent rules in order to identify the most relevant facts from all the data. The correlation engine will be able to generate intelligence to be disseminated to the operators of the system, in order for them to take decisions about the global cyber security state of the port. These advanced modules employ intelligent algorithms, based on techniques such as machine learning, to identify previously unknown attacks.
Global Situation Awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A Hybrid SA (HSA) system receiving both physical and cyber alarms on potential threats from the real world and the cyber space respectively. The HSA application shows the potential consequences/effects of these threats in the other planes including cascading effects. This innovative solution takes into account the real detected alarms of both applications and identifies and evaluates inter-correlations among different potential threats. This way once a real physical and/or cyber threat is detected the potential consequences including cascading effect in both planes (physical and cyber) will be automatically shown to the decisions makers in order to give them a holistic SA on what is happen and how the situation could evolve.

Focus: protection of EU Ports under Transport Infrastructure and means of transportation type of CI.

Decision Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The HSA proposes some decision support actions that could help the decision makers to prevent or even mitigate the future stated consequences.
Alert System and Response	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• An Emergency Population Warning System, allowing local, regional, or national authorities to contact members of rescue/security teams and the public (also integrating Smart City Platforms (SCP)) in order to warn them and draw their attention to an immediate hazard. This will encourage them to take a specific action in response to an emergency event or threat.

2.4.2.3.STOP-IT Project

STOP-IT¹² project - Strategic, Tactical, Operational Protection of water Infrastructure against cyber-physical Threats -, funded under H2020 programme and addresses the topic CIP-01-2016-2017 (i.e., from 01/06/2017 to 31/05/2021). Water critical infrastructures (CIs) are essential for human society, life and health and they can be endangered by physical/cyber threats with severe societal consequences. The STOP-IT project aims at finding solutions to protect critical water infrastructure against physical and cyber threats. STOP-IT will contribute to the human wellbeing and safety through reducing the impacts of both natural hazards and cyber-attacks in the water critical infrastructure analysing current technologies and proposing new palliative actions. The project aims to ensure the resilience and safety of integrated water cycle systems in the face of cyber threats and intentional physical threats.

STOP-IT solutions are based on technologies that include mature technologies, like public warning systems and smart locks that are improved by their combination and embedment, and novel ones such as high-volume real-time sensor data protection via blockchain schemes or efficient water contamination detection algorithms. The Technological Center Eurecat will develop, within the STOP-IT consortium, high-tech tools to prevent cyber-attacks and natural hazards that could jeopardise water supply networks and vital infrastructure for cities. The STOP-IT integrated platform is scalable (scaling from small utilities to large ones), adaptable (including various modules addressing different needs, with expandability for future modules), and flexible (the water utility managers can decide how to use it and it will be usable by experts, novices, and even non-technical staff). It also supports strategic/tactical planning, real time operational decision making and post-action assessment for the key parts of the water infrastructure. Building on this solid basis, STOP-IT delivers high impact through the creation of hands-on training, best practice guidelines, support for certification and standardization as well as by fostering market opportunities, also leveraging the EU water technology platform's multi-stakeholder network. Within Communities of Practice (CoPs), STOP-IT provides space for an effective participation, communication and learning. The CoPs bring together relevant stakeholders and experts for given security issues, developing a common understanding of the advantages and disadvantages of various options for tackling different kinds of threats.

¹² <https://stop-it-project.eu/>

The following Table *Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.*-5 shows the main tools of STOP-IT:

Table Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-5: STOP-IT project's main tools

Focus: Water critical infrastructures	
Risk assessment and treatment framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A risk assessment and treatment framework forms the strategic and tactical decision making element of the overall risk management framework. Innovative solutions for risk treatment (prevention, detection, mitigation and recovery) of critical water infrastructures at the operational level.
Detection and protection against physical and cyber threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Toolbox of technologies for protection against physical threats, such as coordinated network cameras, XACML Authorization Engine, human presence detection using WiFi signals, water quality monitoring technologies for the early detection and impact minimization of contamination events (intentional attacks) and applications to service employees and to central management systems. • Cyber threat incident service • Real-time anomaly detection system
Alert System and Information Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communities of Practice (CoP) for water systems protection serves as a forum to encourage and facilitate information sharing, co-development and transferability amongst infrastructure operators, expert communities and other stakeholders. • A Public warning system allows the information sharing with the public in the areas affected by critical events and improved visualisation interfaces to facilitate the provision of a common operational picture for critical water infrastructure operators

2.4.2.4. SmartResilience Project

The SmartResilience¹³ project - Smart Resilience Indicators for Smart Critical Infrastructures -, funded under the H2020 programme, addresses the topic DRS-14-2015 (From 2016-05-01 to 2019-04-30). SmartResilience significantly improves the resilience of critical infrastructure, such as energy and water supply, transportation and information and communication grids etc., by providing a uniform and comprehensive methodology of risk and resilience assessment. SmartResilience provides solutions that are suitable to enhance the societal resilience in European countries and the organizational resilience among European infrastructure owners. Smart Resilience aims to provide an innovative “holistic” methodology for assessing resilience that is based on resilience indicators. Smart Resilience specific objectives are to identify existing indicators suitable for assessing resilience of smart critical infrastructures (SCIs); to identify new “smart” resilience indicators (RIs); to develop advanced resilience assessment methodology and tools and to test and validate the methodology/tools. Smart Resilience will significantly improve the resilience of SCIs by providing a

¹³ <http://www.smartresilience.eu-vri.eu/>

uniform and comprehensive methodology of risk and resilient assessment. This assessment will lead to proactive innovations that eventually will raise the level of resilience at those SCIs.

SmartResilience develops a new advanced resilience assessment methodology based on a new set of smart Resilience Indicators that enable end-users (authorities, operators and owners of critical infrastructures) to better assess the resilience of the respective infrastructure, especially with respect to future and emerging threats, including those imposed by the enhancement and evolution of critical infrastructures towards “smartness”. This improved assessment methodology is supported by a model to identify interdependencies, between infrastructures as well as between these infrastructures and other sectors. The SmartResilience solutions is delivered in form of a practical guideline and a supporting tool (“SCI Dashboard”) for resilience assessment. SmartResilience is not only focused to technical aspects of resilience. The project covers security needs arising from disaster risks, including threats to life. The main planned results of SmartResilience are a Resilience Assessment Guideline and a tool (“Smart Critical Infrastructure Dashboard”), both aiming at supporting end-users (authorities, critical infrastructure operators and owners) in improving the disaster resilience of respective critical infrastructures through indicator-based assessment of their resilience capabilities. The solutions provided by SmartResilience are oriented towards practical needs of end-users and will be developed in close collaboration with all relevant stakeholders. A resilience management framework includes risk analysis as a central component. Risk analysis depends on characterization of the threats, vulnerabilities and consequences of adverse events to determine the expected loss of critical functionality.

The following Table *Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.*-6 shows the main tools:

Table Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-6: SmartResilience project's main tools

Focus: Smart critical infrastructures (SCIs), such as energy & water supply, transportation and information and communication grids etc.	
Resilience Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identifying existing indicators suitable for assessing resilience of SCIs and new “smart” resilience indicators (RIs) – including those from Big Data. Developing a new advanced resilience assessment methodology based on smart RIs (“resilience indicators cube”, including the resilience matrix). The collected set of indicators is then “checked”, in order to be sure that the whole resilience assessment process is well covered, the indicators are then ordered within the resilience matrix. The matrix looks at the 4 phases of the resilience cycle (prepare, absorb, recover, adapt) and four types of indicators (physical, information, cognitive, social) Developing the interactive “SCI Dashboard” tool

2.4.2.5. DEFENDER Project

DEFENDER¹⁴ project – Defending the European Energy Infrastructure – funded under H2020 programme, addresses the topic CIP-01-2016-2017 (From 01/05/2017 to 31/08/2020). DEFENDER project meets the strategic challenge of protecting the CEI legacy and designing a new generation of

¹⁴ <https://defender-project.eu/>

more resilient European Energy Infrastructure. This new generation of CEI must be able to survive large scale physical and cyber-attacks and incidents, ensuring the continuity of operations and minimizing the effect on the environment, the vicinity and the energy end- users.

DEFENDER adopts a holistic approach, thinking in terms of securing the entire energy infrastructure, considering the whole aspects and not in fragmented terms, in order to enhance both physical and cyber security. The DEFENDER project pursues the following strategic objectives:

Adaptation, integration, implementation, and validation of a range of different technologies and operational projects in order to develop a new approach to safeguard European CEI from cyber, physical and social threats.

Development of new perspectives and methodologies for the lifecycle assessment, resilience and self-healing offering “security by design”.

Development of advanced control systems for incident mitigation and intrusion detection.

Creation of a culture of security where trusted information exchange between trained employees and volunteers will complement cyber-physical protection, while preserving the privacy of the citizens involved.

DEFENDER combines a range of devices/technologies for situational awareness (fixed sensors like Phasor Measurement Units (PMU), mobile devices like drones and advanced video surveillance) (ii) intelligent processing for cyber-physical threat detection with (iii) a toolbox for incident mitigation and emergency response and (iv) Human-In-The-Loop for managing people interaction with CEI, while leveraging on blockchain technology for peer-to-peer trustworthiness.

Different layers where are included sensors and systems to detect, identify, response to, and mitigate anomalies and threats have been identified in the DEFENDER system. Table **Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-7 presents the main tools:

*Table **Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-7: DEFENDER project's main tools*

Focus: Critical Energy Infrastructure	
<p>Source Layer: The Source Layer of the DEFENDER is composed of the set of sensor devices and equipment that are able to communicate and provide information, of any kind, to the DEFENDER system.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cyber sensor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ SCADA ○ Smart meter ○ Integrated security mechanisms (e.g., SIPROTEC 5) ○ Communication network elements (e.g., optical network, SDH, IP/MPLS, DCN, TCP/IP, events, logs, routing tables, topology, configurations) ○ Information System security and protection elements (e.g., firewalls, IDS/IDP and integrity management, events, logs, configurations, reports, network traffic content, protocol headers information, etc.) ○ Information System security management elements (e.g.,

Focus: Critical Energy Infrastructure

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> identity management, access control management, events, logs, configurations, access control enforcement elements events, etc.) ○ Information System application elements (e.g., hosts, virtualized resources, services, events, logs, installations, configurations, DNS, etc.) ○ Operation procedures elements (events, logs) ○ Business procedure elements (events, logs) ● Human sensor ● Physical sensor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Vibration, IR, strain, fiber, etc. ○ Geophone ○ Lidar sensor ○ PMZ camera ○ Thermal camera ○ RF radar
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<p>Event Layer: The Event Layer of the DEFENDER is responsible to identify the threat related events. The Event Layer utilises a specialised module for detecting Cyber-security related events, as well as a second module that identifies physical-security related events. On top of those two components, there is a third one that determines Cyber-Physical events, combining the results of the Cyber Event Detection and the Physical Event Detection.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Physical Detectors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Human Intrusion ○ Person Detection and Tracking ● Cyber Detectors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Network monitoring ○ Pattern Matcher on log data ○ Access Control Event Detection ○ Optical Network Event Detection ○ SCADA Network Inventory Event Detection ○ NORM Event Detection
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<p>Situation Layer: The Situation Layer compiles the overall status of the identified incident and tracks that status over time, creating an overview of the evolved security situation. The objective of the Situation Layer is to transform the events generated from the Event Layer into an assessment of the best actions to mitigate the situation, through controlled Decision Support mechanisms.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Incident Mitigation DSS ● CEI Incidents DSS
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<p>Service Layer:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Security Control Centre ● Action Toolbox
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Focus: Critical Energy Infrastructure	
<p>The Service Layer augments the Situation Layer information with possible counter measures, depending on the characteristics of the security situation. It constitutes a Security Control Centre and provides an Action Toolbox, which can be used to select possible counter measures and actions to heal the consequences of the Cyber or Physical security incident.</p>	
<p>Actuator Layer: contains a set of components to mitigate the cyber-physical threats and attacks by enabling responses using drones, humans and/or virus/malware. Possible countermeasures can include the complete destruction of the attacking drone, the signal interference, so that the drone is disconnected from its controlling point, as well as other non-destructive measures that attempt to neutralise the drone.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drone neutralisation • Fault Location and service recovery • Double Virtualization • Human In the Loop

2.4.2.6. 7SHIELD Project

7SHIELD¹⁵ - Safety and Security Standards of Space Systems, ground Segments and Satellite data assets, via prevention, detection, response and mitigation of physical and cyber threats -, funded under H2020 programme, addresses the topic SU-INFRA01-2018-2019-2020 (From 01/09/2020 to 31/08/2022).

7SHIELD aims at providing a holistic framework enable to confront complex threats by covering all the macro stages of crisis management, namely pre-crisis, crisis and post-crises phases. Specifically, the early warning mechanism estimates the level of risk before the occurrence of a cyber or physical attack. During an attack, the detection and response is effective and efficient, taking into account budgetary constraints. A mitigation plan is designed and automatically updated to offer a quick recovery after an intentional attack or a system failure. Security and resilience of private installations of space ground segments are also supported by business continuity scenarios, building on top of an innovative orchestration of novel monitoring and forecasting technologies. The 7SHIELD's technologies and tools developed in the project are illustrated in Table *Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.*-8.

Table Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-8: 7SHIELD project's main tools

Focus: Space Systems, ground Segments and Satellite data assets
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¹⁵ <https://www.7shield.eu/project/>

Prevention Technologies for Physical and Cyber Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk Assessment tools • Secure authentication mechanism • Combined threat assessment tool • Cyber and Physical Threat Intelligence
Detection Technologies for Physical and Cyber Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data collection and edge processing • Video surveillance technologies (Face detection and face recognition; Video-based object and activity recognition) • Cyber-attack detection framework • Thermal and near-infrared image processing for man-made threats detection • Innovative Laser-based technologies for the detection of ground-based and aerial threats detection • Combined Physical and Cyber Threat Detection and Early Warning
Response Technologies for Physical and Cyber Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Semantic representation and linking for reasoning and decision-making • Crisis level classification from multimodal data fusion • Tactical Decision Support System • Social awareness and warning message generation • UAV neutralisation mechanism
Mitigation Technologies for Physical and Cyber Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential impacts from C/P attacks and countermeasures knowledge base

2.4.2.7. InfraStress Project

InfraStress¹⁶ project - Improving resilience of sensitive industrial plants & infrastructures exposed to cyber-physical threats, by means of open testbed stress-testing system -, funded under H2020 programme, addresses the topic SU-INFRA01-2018-2019-2020 (From 01/06/2019 to 30/09/2021).

The mission of InfraStress is to improve the resilience and the protection capabilities of SIPS exposed to large scale, combined, cyber-physical threats and hazards, guarantee the continuity of operations, while minimizing cascading effects in the infrastructure itself, the environment, the other CIs, and the citizens in vicinity, at reasonable cost. InfraStress technological framework consists of many tools and services able to detect both cyber and physical threats and hazards; integrate C/P situational awareness and resilience; and provide decision support functionalities for the whole CIP lifecycle (preparedness, planning, prevention, detection, mitigation, response, and post-event). The systems and tools are classified as shown in Table Errore. **Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-9.**

¹⁶ <https://www.infrastress.eu/>

Focus: Sensitive industrial plants & infrastructures	
Physical and cyber threats detection and protection systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical threats and hazards detection and protection systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Laser Radar (2D LIDAR) based surveillance ○ Mini-drone detection and neutralization ○ Non-authorized People Detector ○ Building and facility diagnosis and monitoring ○ Environmental monitoring ○ Relevant event and anomaly detection from video surveillance ○ People behaviour analysis from visual data • Cyber threats and hazards detection and protection systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ BAM-Aware Intrusion Detection ○ Machine-learning based Anomaly Based Detection ○ Cyber threat detection at end-points and IIoT/SCADA • Human sensors and crowdsensing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Crowd-sensing apps to get signals from the environment/vicinity ○ Detection of relevant security event and info from OSINT and social media ○ Sentiment and Emotions Detection from social networks
Integrated C/P situational awareness for SIPS CIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Situational picture for integrated cyber-physical protection of industrial sensitive sites and plants <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Relevant event handling and anomaly discovery ○ Resilience indicators dashboard and visual analytics ○ Situational picture dashboard and visual analytics ○ Identification of complex attack scenarios ○ Geospatial stream correlation engine ○ Interdependency and cascading effects impact assessment ○ Multi-dimensional descriptive analytics • Cyber and physical threat intelligence ad prediction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ OSINT/Dark Web analysis for cyber/physical threat intelligence ○ Integration of cyber threat intelligence (TI) sources ○ Spatiotemporal forecasting of attacks and vulnerabilities
Applications and services for C/P protection of resilient industrial sensitive sites and plants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevention and preparedness decision support services <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Building Information Model ○ Vulnerability assessment ○ Security Risk assessment and analysis services ○ Simulation and impact assessment of C/P threats and hazards ○ Service to build integrated safety-security risk management plans ○ Cyber-Physical security and safety design tool to co-design and assess SIP safety/security system ○ Organizational Resilience Culture Audit ○ AR-based Training for CIP

Focus: Sensitive industrial plants & infrastructures

Applications and services for C/P protection of resilient industrial sensitive sites and plants (continued)

- CIP monitoring and early warning services
 - Monitoring and early warning dashboards
- Response, mitigation and recovery decision support services
 - Services improving the protection of first responders
 - Cyber-physical policy enforcement engine
 - Rapid damage assessment
 - Crowdsourcing apps to engage citizens, volunteers, and operators
- Post-event analysis services
 - Prescriptive analytics for CIP improvement
 - Organizational learning STAff RIdE Protocol

2.4.2.8. ENSURESEC Project

ENSURESEC¹⁷ - End-to-end Security of the Digital Single Market's E-commerce and Delivery Service Ecosystem -, funded under H2020 programme, addresses the topic SU-INFRA01-2028-2029-2020 (From 01/06/2020 to 31/05/2022).

ENSURESEC's overarching objective is to equip e-commerce infrastructures and ecosystems with through-life protection against cyber, physical and cyber-physical threats, including cascading effects, thus contributing towards the vision of a reliable and trusted European Digital Single Market.

ENSURESEC includes six main modules:

- Prevention by design: Prevention assesses and certifies that the design of the system interfaces is secure against certain classes of critical attacks and vulnerabilities.
- Detection by monitoring: Detection monitors run-time interface operations at the application level and network level for resilience against both known and unknown threats, i.e., whenever a vulnerability or arbitrary malicious activity is detected, the system continues operation in fail-safe mode
- Response and mitigation of threats and incidents: engine communicates an appropriate response to the affected users and partners and attempts to mitigate the impact
- Recovery of compromised interfaces: recovers the system's state by identifying what has gone wrong based on a dependency-directed diagnosis.
- Continuous situational awareness of threats and incidents.
- Training of SMEs and their citizen clients of e-commerce.

The ENSURESEC concept (Figure Errore. **Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-5) is based on prevention-by-design (combined security-by-design and privacy-by-design) followed by a circular –monitoring – assessing risk – detecting incidents – mitigating risks approach to ensure through-life protection.

¹⁷ <https://www.ensuresec.eu/>

Figure Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-5: The ENSURESEC concept

Table Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-10 illustrates the main tools that have been developed in the project.

Table Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-10: ENSURESEC project's main tools

Focus: e-commerce infrastructures and ecosystems	
<p>Prevention By Design The prevention-by-design module verifies that various models that describe the e-commerce ecosystem are protected against combined cyber-physical, security and privacy threats.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping Engine • Modelling and verification • Continuity management • Ecosystem Risk and Resilience Analyzer
<p>Detection By Monitoring Though protection-by-design assures that the e-commerce ecosystem design is protected and reliable, still the actual functioning of the ecosystem may be compromised as it runs in a hostile environment. Therefore, this module enforces the security of the ecosystem in real-time by monitoring the execution of the interfaces.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Behavioural Monitor • Data security Monitor • Communication Monitor • Policy Monitor • Physical Asset Monitor • AI-based Incident Monitor
<p>Response, Mitigation and Recovery Based on the detection of security incidents, this module is responsible for responding to the incident related business and services partners and their citizen clients on one hand and to initiate a corresponding mitigation strategy to eliminate or reduce the impact of the incident on the other hand. The mitigation strategy first attempts to eliminate the impact of the incident by recovering the compromised interfaces, if that is not possible, then it attempts to reduce the impact of the incident.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Response and Mitigation Engine • Distributed Ledger • Software Recovery Engine • Post-event Analyser
<p>Resilient Oriented Situational Awareness The security of the e-commerce ecosystem involves complex threats with cascading effects and with unique cyber, cyber-physical, physical impacts. Therefore, this module goes beyond classical security situational analysis tools and aims to employ advanced machine learning and data analysis techniques to continuously</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events Correlation Engine • Information Sharing • (Cyber and Physical) Threat Intelligence • Multi-level Interdependency and Cascading Effect Analyzer • Visual Analyzer

Focus: e-commerce infrastructures and ecosystems

perform situational analysis of suspected and current incidents and to determine their impact.

2.4.2.9. PANOPTIS Project

The PANOPTIS¹⁸ project – Development of a Decision Support System for increasing the Resilience of Transportation Infrastructure based on combined use of terrestrial and airborne sensors and advanced modelling tools -, funded under H2020 programme, addresses the topic MG-7-1-2017 (From 01/06/2018 to 31/05/2022).

The project aimed at the development of a Decision Support System for increasing the Resilience of Road Infrastructure based on combined use of terrestrial and airborne sensors and advanced modelling tools. The purpose of PANOPTIS project was to improve the resiliency (ability to adapt) of the road infrastructures and ensuring reliable network availability under unfavourable conditions, such as extreme weather, landslides, and earthquakes. The project’s main goal was to combine down-scale climate change scenarios (applied to road infrastructure) with structural and geotechnical simulation tools, and with actual data from sensors (terrestrial and airborne), in order to provide the operators with an integrated tool able to support more effective management of their infrastructures at planning, maintenance and operation level.

Table Errore. **Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-11 illustrates the main tools that have been developed in the project.

Table Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-11: PANOPTIS project's main tools

Focus: improve the resiliency (ability to adapt) of the road infrastructures	
<p>Tool: Integrated Incident Management & Decision Support System for Road Operators</p> <p>PANOPTIS aimed to design and develop a next generation Situation Management & Decision Support System that combines:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Various Road Infrastructure Sensors • Aerial Platforms • Deep Learning based Video Analytics • Weather Modelling Tools • Structural Modelling Tools • Risk and Impact Assessment Tools • Resources and Assets • Geographical information systems
<p>Main purposes of the tool</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand RI resilience to atmospheric and geotechnical hazards • Manage planned and planned events / incidents with Decision Support • Acquire Early Warning and Situational Awareness capabilities • Respond via Standard Operating Procedures
<p>Main benefits of the tool</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software-as-a-Service or on Premise

¹⁸ <http://www.panoptis.eu/>

Focus: improve the resiliency (ability to adapt) of the road infrastructures

- Integration of unique and diverse tools and services for RI Situational Awareness & Decision Support
 - Prediction Services
 - Impact Assessment Services
 - Warning & Alerts
 - Specialized Video Analytics
 - What if / What is
- Standard Operating Procedures fully customizable by RI Operators
- Data on the Move

2.4.2.10. SAFECARE Project

SAFECARE¹⁹ project - SAFEGuard of Critical heAlth infrastructure-, funded under H2020 programme, addresses the topic CIP-01-2016-2017 (From 01/09/2018 to 30/11/2021).

The aim of the SAFECARE is to provide solutions that will improve physical and cyber security in a seamless and cost-effective way. It promotes new technologies and novel approaches to enhance threat prevention, threat detection, incident response and mitigation of impacts. The project outcomes contribute to increase compliance between security tools and European regulations about ethics and privacy for health services. The end goal of the SAFECARE project is to protect healthcare infrastructures, and eventually the safety of the patient, by fostering the creation of solutions for the improvement of cyber and physical security in the current healthcare context. SAFECARE global solution has been designed for the improvement of cyber and physical security in the healthcare context.

The SAFECARE global architecture can be broken down into 3 parts:

- Physical security solutions
- Cyber security solutions
- Integrated cyber-physical security solutions.

The physical security solutions and the cyber security solutions consist of smart modules and efficient integrated technologies to respectively improve physical security and cyber security. More specifically, physical security solutions embed integrated intelligent video monitoring and interconnect building monitoring systems as well as management systems. Meanwhile, cyber security solutions correspond to cyber monitoring systems as well as threat detection systems related to information technology (IT), building management system (BMS) and e-health systems. Both physical security solutions and cyber security solutions are interconnected thanks to the integrated cyber-physical security solutions. The integrated cyber-physical security solutions consist of intelligent modules whose role is to integrate different data sources and better take into account the combination of physical and cyber security threats²⁰. The main project's tools are shown in Table **Error! Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-12.

¹⁹ <https://www.safecare-project.eu/>

²⁰ White Book - Deliverable 8.4. SAFECARE project. 2021

Table *Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.*-12: SAFECARE project's main tools

Focus: healthcare context	
Physical security solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The suspicious behaviour detection system (SBDS) • The intrusion and fire detection system (IFDS) • The data collection system (DCS) • The mobile alerting system (MAS) • The building threat monitoring system (BTMS)
Cyber security solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The IT threat detection system (ITTDS) • The BMS threat detection system (BTDS) • The advanced file analysis system (AFAS) • The e-health devices security analytics (EDSA) • The cyber threat monitoring system (CTMS)
Integrated cyber-physical security solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The data exchange layer (DXL) • The central database (CDB) • The impact propagation and decision support model (IPDSM) • The threat response and alert system (TRAS) • The hospital availability management system (HAMS) • The e-health security risk management model

2.4.2.11. SATIE Project

SATIE²¹ project - Security of Air Transport Infrastructure of Europe -, funded under H2020 programme, addresses the topic SU-INFRA01-2018-2019-2020 (From 01/05/2019 to 31/10/2021).

SATIE's ambition was to design, develop, integrate and demonstrate a set of different Innovation Elements (IEs) in order to improve the state of the art in airport security by solving the pre-identified conceptual, technical, economical, and societal limitations. SATIE adopted a holistic approach about threat prevention, detection, response and mitigation in the airports, while guaranteeing the protection of critical systems, sensitive data and passengers. Critical assets are usually protected against individual physical or cyber threats, but not against complex scenarios combining both categories of threats. In order to handle it, SATIE developed an interoperable toolkit which improves cyber-physical correlations, forensics investigations and dynamic impact assessment at airports.

The type of the classification adopted in the project to classify the systems and technologies provided was organized around the phases of the crisis management (threat prevention, detection, response and mitigation).

More specifically, in the context of the project several Security Solutions are deployed in critical areas in order to detect and prevent potential threats in airport environments. A **Correlation Engine** gathers information coming from detectors and airport systems and triggers aggregated alerts in real time.

²¹ <https://satie-h2020.eu/>

Two **Impact Propagation Tools** relying on an interdependency model between IT assets, airport operations, and business processes, provide an impact assessment and decision support to the **Security Operation Centre (SOC)** and the **Airport Operation Centre (AOC)**.

An **Investigation Tool** unifies the physical and cyber security investigation and performs a deep analysis of activities and threats over a long time-frame to identify alerts stemming from the same attack.

For the operator in the SOC, an **Incident Management Portal (IMP)** displays aggregated alerts and provides contextual information about security events, targeted assets, and exploitable vulnerabilities.

For those in the AOC, a **Crisis Alerting System (CAS)** improves collaboration and coordination with the SOC, first responders, and other airport stakeholders for a faster security and safety response²². The main project's tools are shown in Table *Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.*-13.

Table Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-13: SATIE project's main tools

Focus: Security of Air Transport Infrastructure of Europe	
Correlation Engine (Prevention, Detection)	<p>The Correlation Engine is the central system of the SATIE Toolkit whose objective it is to aggregate and correlate information from the entire SATIE Toolkit. The Correlation Engine triggers alerts to the Incident Management Portal based on a set of user-defined correlation rules. The Correlation Engine aggregates information from the entire SATIE Toolkit (cyber and physical events). Alerts raised by the Correlation Engine are forwarded to the IMP and presented to the SOC operator in one of four severity levels (high, medium, low, info).</p> <p>The Correlation Engine as the core system of the SATIE Toolkit aggregates data from cyber and physical events from other Supporting Systems and the Threat Prevention and Detection Systems to correlate them based on a set of specified rules. Information on detected threats is forwarded to the Incident Management Portal. The information is presented in a consolidated way to the SOC operators.</p>
Impact Propagation Tools (Response, Impact mitigation)	<p>Within the SATIE toolkit, two Impact Propagation Tools visualize the impact of attacks on the cyber and physical assets, passengers, staff, and business processes to provide decision support to the SOC and AOC operators and assist in impact mitigation. These are the Impact Propagation Simulation and the Business Impact Assessment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Impact Propagation Simulation focusses on how an attack's impact propagates through the airport's assets and influences passengers' behaviour by employing the combination of two propagation models: A Network Model and an Agent-based Model (ABM).

²² Fabian Reuschling, Nils Carstengerdes, Tim H. Stelkens-Kobsch, Kelly Burke, Thomas Oudin, Meilin Schaper, Filipe Apolinário, Isabel Praça and Leonidas Perlepes (2021). Toolkit to Enhance Cyber-physical Security of Critical Infrastructures in Air Transport. s.l. : Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence for Critical Infrastructures Security.

Focus: Security of Air Transport Infrastructure of Europe

- **The Network Model** is a topological representation of the cyber and physical assets – including airport staff and passengers – as nodes (shown as numbered circles) and their interconnections, e.g. information flows or wiring, as edges (shown as lines connecting the circles).
- **The Agent-based Model** is employed to simulate the physical movement of passengers at the airport. The central infrastructures – doors, check-in areas, security controls, Flight Information Display System monitors, and gates – are approximated and visually modelled.
- The **Business Impact Assessment** as second Impact Propagation Tool analyses how business-critical processes and goals are affected by an attack. The impact assessment is performed to identify assets in the airport’s infrastructure affected by threat propagation and determine the critical services compromised. The assessment further analyses the impacts the affected services may cause on the airport’s business-critical processes.

The main purpose of the Impact Propagation Simulation is to provide information on how an attack’s impact propagates through the airport’s assets and influences passengers’ behaviour, while the **Business Impact Assessment** as second Impact Propagation Tool analyses how business-critical processes and goals are affected by an attack. The SOC and AOC operators are employed with both, a holistic overview of impacted assets and details of how airport processes are affected and the impacts of the affected services on the airport’s business-critical processes.

Investigation Tools (Response, Impact mitigation)

The **Investigation Tool** developed (SMS-I), represents SATIE’s innovation in what concerns the need to deal with the analysis of data from heterogeneous systems, over different time frames, and to provide insights about evidence of the causes of an attack. SMS-I is a tool that receives events and alerts from the Correlation Engine and incidents marked by the SOC operator within the Incident Management Portal. The Investigation Tool (SMS-I) unifies the physical and cybersecurity investigation. It performs a deep analysis of activities and threats over a long timeframe to identify, in real-time, alerts stemming from the same attack. SMS-I also supports the fast recovery in case of an incident by analysing past mitigation strategies using Machine Learning (ML) techniques.

Security investigation aims to explore the cause of an attack and how much it threatened the security of the targeted property. In case the security of a system is compromised, investigating over the information collected during the monitoring phase can bring important insights, both to improve detection and prevention, and to support mitigation and remediation strategies.

Incident Management

The **Incident Management Portal** is the main system interacted with by the SOC operator. Through two software solutions, CymID and

Focus: Security of Air Transport Infrastructure of Europe

Portal (Response, Impact mitigation)

Cymerius, it offers a central place to access all Supporting Systems and Threat Prevention and Detection Systems that provide a Graphical User Interface (GUI). Furthermore, all alerts raised by the SATIE Tools are aggregated here and can be managed, analysed, and shared with the Crisis Alerting System. The design of the Incident Management Portal is suitable to be used in all environments and provides a global and coherent approach to the monitoring of information systems' security. It continuously provides the key indicators on the security of the system together with relevant information, so that the severity and consequences of a complex attack or major alert are understood by all SOC operators, independent of their level and scope of duties. The CymID software is a Single Sign-On (SSO) solution enabling the SOC operator to access a multitude of tools without them having to sign in for each separately.

The Incident Management Portal displays aggregated alerts and provides contextual information about security events, targeted assets, and exploitable vulnerabilities to the SOC operators.

The design of the Incident Management Portal is suitable to be used in all environments and provides a global and coherent approach to the monitoring of information systems' security. It continuously provides the key indicators on the security of the system together with relevant information, so that the severity and consequences of a complex attack or major alert are understood by all SOC operators, independent of their level and scope of duties.

Crisis Alerting System (CAS) (Response, Impact mitigation)

The Crisis Alerting System is the main tool used by the AOC operators, improving the communication between SOC and AOC operators, and the decision-making and incident management process. Additionally, CAS enables communication among the AOC operators and the first responders, airport stakeholders, and citizens that are close to the airport or are using the airport facilities and could therefore be affected by an incident.

AOC operators are able to monitor the airport by checking the information coming from its various security and safety systems (e.g. CCTV cameras). This information is depicted in the CAS's Graphical User Interface and enhanced with information produced by the SOC and the Impact Propagation Simulation. In that way, AOC operators are able to have a better view of the situation at the airport, consequently improving their response activities, like informing affected passengers and contacting first responders. Additionally, standard operating procedures in the form of action lists are depicted to the operators, guiding their actions. Moreover, the Crisis Alerting System enables communication between the AOC operators and the third-party agencies that are responsible to respond to an emergency situation. In case of an emergency, AOC operators are able to communicate with safety agencies, such as the Fire Service, the Emergency Medical Service, etc., sharing operation information useful to the situation. This communication between the AOC operators and involved agencies improves the situation

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awareness, collaboration, and the coordination of the response activities. In cases where the notification of citizens is required, AOC operators (through CAS) are able to alert them. The smart notification service takes into account the characteristics of a situation (such as the location, type, criticality, etc.) in order to route the notification only to citizens that are close to or affected by the situation.

The main benefits of the System are as follows:

The **generation of the operational picture** by combining information from security and safety systems of the airport with information provided by the SOC and the Impact Propagation Simulation.

Smart notification and alerting service enables the information sharing among involved actors at every level of coordination during a crisis by enabling collaborative response and at the same time supporting multichannel alerting of passengers and of possibly affected population, with variable content according to their location.

2.4.2.12. SPHINK Project

SPHINX²³ project - A Universal Cyber Security Toolkit for Health-Care Industry-, funded under H2020 programme, addresses the topic SU-TDS-02-2018 (From 01/01/2019 to 31/03/2022).

SPHINX aimed to introduce a health tailored Universal Cyber Security Toolkit, thus enhancing the cyber protection of the Health and Care IT Ecosystem and ensuring patients' data privacy and integrity. It also provided an automated zero-touch device and service verification toolkit that can be easily adapted or embedded on existing, medical, clinical or health available infrastructures.

SPHINX brought a Universal **Cyber Security Toolkit** for the Health and Care Domain that enhances the cyber protection of the healthcare IT ecosystem and ensures the patients' data privacy and integrity. The SPHINX toolkit offers an embedded, smart and robust security awareness layer, able to identify modern and advance cyber threats, enhanced with a personalised data security management tool. This is a suite of tools, targeted for protecting the healthcare sector infrastructures. Some of the tools, work for vulnerability or attack prevention and detection while other tools take these events as inputs to raise combined alerts or react to the threat. This is an integrated set of tools for securing healthcare infrastructure and data. The SPHINX suite is an integrated and certified set of tools, covering a wide range of scenarios to secure a hospital.

- **Decision Support System (DSS):** Decision support system for healthcare. Integrated into SPHINX suite. This tool aims to predict attacks by using ML but also mitigate in real time some attacks onto the healthcare infrastructure. Detection of insights before an attack has been successfully performed and reactive execution of countermeasures to mitigate. The Decision Support System is an engine developed for the SPHINX Toolkit based on Docker framework making it suitable for cloud and on-premise installations. The DSS has two Functionalities. The Proactive functionality uses the network traffic to predict an upcoming cyber-attack and notifies

²³ <https://sphinx-project.eu/>

the user of the attack and suggests a fast reaction like blocking the attacker's IP address. To achieve this, the solution relies on the advances of Machine Learning Algorithms. The Active functionality suggests a targeted response plan based on attack and the combination of the information from other components.

- **Real-time Cyber Risk Assessment (RCRA):** The Real-time Cyber Risk assessment (RCRA), assesses the risk of cyber-security incidents and indication of probable consequences, taking information from vulnerability reports, logs and data from other SPHINX components, and format them into common identifiers and descriptions from security knowledge databases (VCDB, MITRE or NVD). Periodic risk estimation of a healthcare infrastructure. Risk analyser from inputs of other security tools in the SPHINX suite.
- **Vulnerability Assessment as a Service (VAaaS):** The Vulnerability Assessment as a Service (VAaaS) is a system of automatic assessment of vulnerabilities inside a network. It offers seamless assessment for all existing and newly introduced network entities against all known security vulnerabilities, certifies them through a Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS), classifies them according to the cyber-threat they introduce, and finally assigns them to a connectivity-appropriate VLAN.
- **Analytics Engine:** SPHINX Analytics Engine is based on Docker framework making it suitable for cloud and on-premise installations. The Analytics engine provides the ability to monitor how many attacks identified and the attack events based on historical data for a time interval. It Provides bar plots used for the visualization of the identified event and provides all the required information to address future events. The information can be used from other cybersecurity services and end-users to detect suspicious or malicious cyber activities, identify their type and do appropriate courses of action that can be used to stop the detected attacks and vulnerabilities.
- **Blockchain-based Threat Registry Platform (BBTR):** The BBTR is a tool that provides a shared registry of threats by using an Hyperledger Fabric blockchain network. It also provides a listener tool that enables the final users to subscribe to real-time events from the blockchain, allowing them to know when a new threat has been submitted. A user-friendly frontend has also been developed so final users can use a web interface to interact with the BBTR, for purposes such as auditability among others.
- **Service Integration middleware:** Software solution in the form of an integration middleware for bridging third parties' software components, each focused on different functions of a cybersecurity toolbox.
- **Machine Learning-empowered Intrusion Detection using Honeypot's data (MLID):** The Automated Intrusion detection solution transforms multi-dimensional network traffic data generated from honeypots into an actionable and easy-to-understand indicator for security experts. To achieve this, the solution relies on state-of-the-art data mining algorithms and the latest advances in machine learning and deep learning networks.
- **Artificial Intelligence Honeypots:** AI Honeypots of SPHINX are realised both as virtual and hardware appliances. The virtual one is based on docker framework making it suitable for both cloud and on-premise installations; the hardware one mainly suited for on-premise installations comes in two flavours, the first one based on a low-cost Advanced RISC Machine (ARM) system – Quad-core Cortex-A7 central processing unit (CPU) – that is able to support lightweight detection algorithms whereas the second one is capable of operating as a honeypot and a router system, with the capability of handling computing-intensive algorithms without a noticeable delay for the attacker. To achieve this, the system utilises programmable logic in the form of a compact low power field-programmable gate array (FPGA) module. SPHINX AI Honeypots are to be part of an organisation's cyber defence arsenal aiming to detect manifested cyber-attacks as early as possible

by luring the adversaries to attack them instead of the real production IT systems. In this direction, the honeypots host vulnerable services that may be considered targets from an adversary.

- **Cybersecurity Knowledge Base (KB):** Cybersecurity Knowledge Base (KB) repository plays a key role in collaborative threat analysis, automated threat exchange and automated detection and response. In this direction, it stores and offers cyber threat intelligence (CTI) information (e.g. attack patterns, vulnerabilities, threat indicators, etc) using the OASIS STIX (Structured Threat Information Expression) language. The KB information can be used from other cybersecurity services, such as threat detection engines, Honeypots, Decision Support systems to detect suspicious or malicious cyber activities, identify their type and recommend appropriate courses of action that can be used to address the detected attacks and vulnerabilities. Besides enabling its users to register new attack patterns and vulnerabilities, the KB additionally collects threat intelligence knowledge from third-party threat intelligence share repositories such as NIST's National Vulnerability Database and MITRE's Common Attack Pattern Enumeration and Classification towards capturing the latest screenshot of the continuous evolving cybersecurity threat landscape.
- **API for Third Parties (S-API):** The SPHINX API for Third Parties is an innovation based on a programmatic interface that enables developers of medical devices or specialised clinical software to access the available SPHINX services to validate whether their devices, systems or applications are compatible with the high cybersecurity levels upheld by the SPHINX System, thus receiving a SPHINX certification. The assets that present cybersecurity vulnerabilities receive a detailed report identifying the changes required to be implemented so that those devices, systems or applications may obtain the SPHINX certification and become a trusted asset.
- **Homomorphic Encryption (HE):** The Homomorphic Encryption Tool is in the form of computation time, particularly the time taken for data anonymization and the time taken for search in the encrypted database. It also logs the time taken for the decryption process.
- **Security Protocol Analysis (SPA):** The SPA allows researchers to define and test security protocols. It provides an expressive formal language for specifying security protocols and their properties along with automatic analysis techniques.
- **Forensic Data Collection Engine (FDCE):** The FDCE component supports the processing and storage of data gathered from various sources in a unified structure in order to discover the relationships between devices and the evidence and produce a timeline of the incident, including a map of affected devices and a set of a meaningful chain of evidence (linked evidence).
- **Attack and Behaviour Simulators (ABS):** The ABS component is a framework capable of simulating user behaviour inside a network through automated procedures and user profiling procedures based on real network data. Also, it comes with a series of virtual machine-based environments capable of reproducing various attack and malicious behaviour patterns.
- **Anomaly Detection (AD):** Anomaly Detection component is based on both machine learning algorithms and statistics-based algorithms. The AD thus performs a fast and efficient analysis of packets in a network and detects unknown attacks, in part due to the rapid development of malware.
- **Interactive Dashboards (ID):** Interactive Dashboards (ID) is a component that centralizes and converts data (web traffic, alerts) obtained from other SPHINX components in different types of graphical representations (tables, graphs, diagrams and custom plugins) to offer IT staff a faster and more compact interpretation of the network system. ID represents the entry point for users to the SPHINX system.
- **Data Traffic Monitoring (DTM)** is a SPHINX component responsible for threat identification by monitoring the network traffic and applying signature-based detection analysis. It monitors all the packets traversing the network and compares them against a database of attack signatures or

attributes of known malicious threats. Data Traffic Monitoring (DTM) is an intrusion detection system (IDS).

- **Security Information and Event Management (SIEM):** The SIEM tool plays a key role in real-time threats detection by monitoring logs, flows and events of applications, networks, operational systems, devices and many other data sources. The SIEM Agent is responsible for monitoring any asset output and sending it to SIEM ingestor component that parses the raw data into custom source types before being stored in the central log repository. The SIEM real-time monitoring component brings pre-built use cases based on the MITRE's knowledge base attacks tactics and is responsible to raise alerts when malicious activity is identified. SIEM has a user-friendly interface that enables use cases, dashboards and schedulers configuration. To facilitate threat hunting and event correlation the SIEM UI still has a search tool where all the central log repositories can be queried in a query language of the security operator's choice.

2.4.2.13. PRECINCT Project

PRECINCT²⁴ project - Preparedness and Resilience Enforcement for Critical INfrastructure Cascading Cyberphysical Threats and effects with focus on district or regional protection -, funded under H2020 programme, addresses the topic SU-INFRA01-2028-2019-2020 (From 01/10/2021 to 30/09/2023).

Moving from traditional risk analysis to resilience analysis and management allows for resilience-driven risk control by taking appropriate measures in all security and resilience management phases: preparation and prevention (risk probability reduction), protection (consequence impact reduction), attack detection and identification response and recovery (linked to mitigation and fast recovery).

The resilience cycle (Figure Errore. *Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.*-6) illustrates that there cannot be an end in efforts to make a system more resilient. Resilience is a property of dynamic, adaptable systems and not a static condition which can be reached permanently.

²⁴ <https://www.precinct.info/>

Figure *Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.*-6: Resilience cycle

A resilient system differs from others mainly in its ability to respond dynamically to constant changes in its environment and to adapt to unforeseen events. It is not important what measures the system or its operators take to ensure and enhance resilience. In this sense, resilience is a holistic way of thinking about security²⁵.

PRECINCT is positioned in the context of a geographical area in which security and resilience of the CI systems of systems is managed in a coordinated way. The overall project's technical objective is to establish an Ecosystem Platform for connecting stakeholders of interdependent CIs and Emergency Services to collaboratively and efficiently manage security and resilience by sharing data, CIP models and related new resilience services encapsulated in Digital Twins. The broad spectrum of cyber-physical security management is covered:

- **Forecasting**
 - PRECINCT Digital Twins Architecture supporting Cyber-physical Security and Resilience management in interdependent CIs through Digital Twins. Big Data Analytics (BDA) infrastructural services, integrated with NLP services for media analysis linked to hybrid threats, to support predictive and prescriptive real-time analytics linked to Digital Twins.
 - Tools to support the development of PRECINCT Digital Twins (DTs) focusing on interfacing with AI platforms /Neural nets - Serious Games - Cyber Range laboratory. Predictive long-term resilience and security threat and fault behaviour and machine learning prediction algorithms leading to attack forecasting (approach, severity, level, scope etc.).
- **Assessment**
 - Achieved through risk & resilience management matrix and assessment model. Resilience Methodological Framework to facilitate resilience quantification (Resilience Index), supporting the identification of short- and long-term measures that enhance resilience.

²⁵ Thoma, K., Scharte, B., Hiller, D., Leismann, T. (2016). Resilience Engineering as Part of Security Research: Definitions, Concepts and Science Approaches, European Journal for Security Research, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s41125-016-0002-4>

- Vulnerability assessment through Multi-agent Serious Games - Spatial Database Management System. Serious Game Tools inclusive of technologies to represent cascading effects in co-dependent CIs and utilization of the infrastructure components. Data Mining of Game Play Recordings to Identify Vulnerabilities to Cascading Cyber-Physical Threats.
- BDA infrastructural services and common data analytics visualizer to support prescriptive real-time multi-hazard analytics. Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Big Data Analytics (BDA) infrastructure services integrated with Natural Language Processing services for ingesting data from different sources to support predictive and prescriptive real-time analytics linked to Digital Twins.
- **Detection**
 - Achieved by combining Digital Twins models specifically detection algorithms, with BDA recipes retrained and re-validated through Serious Games integrating multi-layered cyber-physical detection frameworks automated false positive mitigation- and have a human in the loop for certain situations.
- **Prevention**
 - Automated prevention/blocking actions automatically implemented (Library of PRECINCT Digital Twins models). PRECINCT Digital Twin Instantiation providing a generic application that will be customised for deployment in each LL.
 - Unified PRECINCT situation awareness user interface (UI) supporting and unifying the ecosystem of portal participants across the LL verticals.
 - Innovative Prevention Models, refined and extended by the gaming related outputs and Integration with Digital Twins to Generate Probabilistic Response Functions and to validate/refine/discover new CIP models.
- **Response**
 - Achieved through GIS based Resilience Management Matrix and resilience/response actions taking into account the cascading effects measures through Development of improved real-time, evidence-based security and resilience management of physical and cyber threats driven by LL requirements. A design studio to support design and implementation of new services compliant with the PRECINCT Framework Specification and supporting initial LL requirements and requests arising from LL operations.
- **Consequences Mitigation**
 - Achieved via short term and long-term enhancements resulting from the application of the Resilience Methodological Framework.
 - Machine learning and unsupervised learning threat mitigation algorithms providing automated recommendations and actions,
 - Advanced situational awareness and workflow-based communications management and coordination.

The review of the previous EU-funded security projects revealed the multidimensionality of the CIP measures and systems. There are several ways in which security products and systems can be categorised depending on the technology itself and the context within which it is used. Technologies can also be categorised and understood as responses to particular threats, or in relation to concerns. Another type of classification is related to the phases of crisis management. The analysis of the CIR/CIP measures and systems will be expanded in future reports.

2.4.3. Notable Outcomes of EU CIP/CIR Projects

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

The technological and methodological outcomes of the EU CIP/CIR projects are important for enhancing the security and resilience of critical infrastructure systems, promoting collaboration and information sharing, advancing the state of the art, and meeting regulatory requirements. The following paragraphs illustrate some of the most notable outcomes (as rated by the project coordinators) of EU CIP/CIR projects, which reflect the state of the art in technologies and measures for protecting critical infrastructures. Along with technological outcomes, a set of non-technological outcomes (e.g., ethics/legal related results) are outlined.

2.4.3.1. Technological Outcomes

Main Technological Outcomes of 7SHIELD

The project has provided a holistic framework that confronts complex threats by covering all the macro stages of crisis management, namely pre-crisis, crisis and post-crises phases. The main technological outcomes of 7SHIELD's technologies have been illustrated in Table **Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-8**.

Main Technological Outcomes of Cybersane

The project has produced:

- An Assessment of Deep web, LifeNet and creation of a Hybridnet
- The CYBERSANE core i.e., the core infrastructure for Security and Privacy Incident Handling, towards security incident detection and handling.
- A Quick response system.
- An Efficient threat monitoring and threat detection system.

Main Technological Outcomes of DEFENDER

DEFENDER has combined a range of devices/technologies for situational awareness (fixed sensors like PMUs, mobile devices like drones and advanced video surveillance) (ii) intelligent processing for cyber-physical threat detection with (iii) a toolbox for incident mitigation and emergency response and (iv) Human-In-The-Loop for managing people interaction with CEI, while leveraging on blockchain technology for peer-to-peer trustworthiness. Different layers where are included sensors and systems to detect, identify, response to, and mitigate anomalies and threats have been identified in the DEFENDER system. An overview of relevant technological outcomes per project are illustrated in Table **Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-7**, which presents the tools of the project.

Main Technological Outcomes of Digital Water City

Digital Water City has produced the following technological outcomes:

- A risk management guide, in which for each step of the risk management process, the user can find an overview of the approaches, methods, tools to be used to protect water infrastructure against cyber-physical threats.

- A web-based database including 68 type of risk events specific to sewer management.
- A set of security checklists supporting both technology providers and water utilities.

Main Technological Outcomes of ENSURESEC

ENSURESEC has produced the following six main modules:

- Prevention by design: Prevention assesses and certifies that the design of the system interfaces is secure against certain classes of critical attacks and vulnerabilities.
- Detection by monitoring: Detection monitors run-time interface operations at the application level and network level for resilience against both known and unknown threats, i.e., whenever a vulnerability or arbitrary malicious activity is detected, the system continues operation in fail-safe mode.
- Response and mitigation of threats and incidents: engine communicates an appropriate response to the affected users and partners and attempts to mitigate the impact.
- Recovery of compromised interfaces: recovers the system's state by identifying what has gone wrong based on a dependency-directed diagnosis.
- Continuous situational awareness of threats and incidents.
- Training of SMEs and their citizen clients of e-commerce.

Main Technological Outcomes of EU-HYBNET

The project has produced:

- A social media radar for monitoring creation of radical protests movement supported by third-party state. e.g., Anti5G, COVID-19.

Main Technological Outcomes FINSEC

FINSEC has produced the following technological outcomes:

- A Cyber Physical Threat Intelligence Platform.
- A Blockchain infrastructure for Trusted Information Sharing
- A Modelling approach for Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence (FINSTIX).
- An Adaptive and Intelligent Security Monitoring Infrastructure for Critical Infrastructures of the finance sector.
- Anomaly detection solutions for Infrastructures of the Financial Sector.

Main Technological Outcomes of InfraStress

The InfraStress technological framework comprises many tools and services able to:

- Detect both cyber and physical threats and hazards.
- Integrate C/P situational awareness and resilience.
- Provide decision support functionalities for the whole CIP lifecycle (preparedness, planning, prevention, detection, mitigation, response, and post-event).

Main Technological Outcomes of PRAETORIAN

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

The main technological outcomes of PRAETORIAN, include:

- A set of Efficiency Prevention and Visualisation Tools (Cyber and Physical Threats)
- A dedicated Digital Twin for Industrial Processes that enables new approaches for Risk Analysis.
- A Threat propagation system based on a generic digital twin.
- A Warning system, that supports cascading effects on other sectors.
- A system for information correlation from cyber and physical situation awareness to detect cascading effects; digital twins and information sharing with multiple CIs.
- A Cyber Situation Awareness System.
- A Physical Situation Awareness System.
- A Coordinated Response System.

Main Technological Outcomes of RESISTO

RESISTO has focused on the protection and resilience of critical infrastructures in the communication sector. It has produced the following main results:

- Vulnerability models for physical and cyber threats of telecom CI.²⁶
- Software Defined Security System and Decision Making Module.²⁷
- Evaluation of interdependencies among different processes in extremely connected and interconnected infrastructures, like Telco operators, including cascading effects, involving also different types of CIs, approaching the complexity with shorter-term prediction models and longer terms analysis for adaptation of the protection measures, called Short Term Control Loop and Long Term Control Loop.
- A Unified security platform for a complete security picture and incident response management.
- Integrated security governance solutions for physical and security.
- Integrated communication for speed response,

Main Technological Outcomes of SAFECARE

SAFECARE has produced the following technological outcomes:

- An IT threat detection system.
- A BMS threat detection system.
- An Advanced file analysis system.

A detailed presentation of SAFECARE tools is included in Table Errore. **Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-12.

Main Technological Outcomes of SAFETY4RAILS

²⁶ http://www.resistoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/Attachment_0-10.pdf

²⁷ http://www.resistoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/RESISTO_D5.2_191128_01.pdf

The main technological results of the project include:

- A platform (S4RIS) combining 10+ tools to prevent, detect, respond and recover from cyber-physical attacks in the railway sector.²⁸
- The SAFETY4RAILS Information System (S4RIS) platform.
- RAM2, an industrial digital and cybersecurity platform for risk monitoring, assessment and management. It integrates with a wide variety of security and industrial systems to collect and correlate data and events, to provide complete asset inventory visibility, identify vulnerabilities, evaluate the security posture, and detect suspicious patterns. RAM2 prioritizes and alerts on risks and provides clear risk mitigation steps, which are feasible within the operational constraints.
- CuriX, a commercial tool to monitor technical devices (e.g., IT, OT) in real-time. It monitors the system behaviour, learns normal behaviour based on statistical and machine learning methods, and informs the users about deviations.
- A pool of tools to be employed for operators working in the safety & security area inside the railways and metro stations addressing prevention, detection, response and assessment. Specifically:
 - 7 tools provide monitoring and infrastructure services related to security, network infrastructure and CCTV data stream analysis.
 - 8 tools provide an intersection of monitoring, simulation and decision support services. These are made possible through the use of intelligent risk assessment mechanisms and provide further mitigation insights through decision support functionality.
 - 4 tools provide simulation services such as agent-based crowd simulation and bomb blast simulation scenarios allowing for security and resilience assessment of stations.

Main Technological Outcomes of SATIE

The main technological results of the project include:

- A security management system (operationally applicable), for threat prediction, impact propagation, which is available at TRL 7.²⁹
- Impact propagation tools, correlation engine, Anomaly Detection on Passenger Records system.
- Tools and techniques for correlating cyber and physical events, including a Risk Assessment Methodology and Usage of digital twin in an effective way.

Main Technological Outcomes of Sauron

The main technological outcome of the project is the SAURON platform, which consists of four main pillars:

- **PSA: A complete Physical SA** system which includes novel features such as; dynamic location of resources and assets, location, management and monitoring of sensors, including cameras mounted on drones, security perimeter control, robust and secure tactical communication network and so on.

²⁸ <https://safety4rails.eu/library/>

²⁹ <https://www.nowpublishers.com/article/Chapter/9781680838220?cId=978-1-68083-823-7.ch11>

- **CSA: An advanced and scalable Cyber SA** framework capable of preventing and detecting threats and in case of a declared attack, capable of mitigating the effects of the infection/intrusion. This CSA system will include new visualization paradigms for the cyber space.
- **HSA: A Hybrid SA system receiving both physical and cyber alarms** on potential threats from the real world and the cyber space respectively.
- **EPWS: An Emergency Population Warning System**, allowing local, regional, or national authorities to contact members of rescue/security teams and the public (also integrating Smart City Platforms (SCP)) in order to warn them and draw their attention to an immediate hazard.

Main Technological Outcomes of SecureGas:

SecureGas has focused on CIP/CIR for gas infrastructures. The project has produced the following main outcomes:

- Technologies for situational awareness and DSS for CP threats, including a Safety & Security platform for gas, an Autonomous docking station for UAV and an Onshore landslide susceptibility and alert monitoring system.
- Technologies for information processing and management (e.g., CP correlator, blockchain for data transmission and integrity verification, cyber security for IT and OT network weakness and IT processing platform).
- Technologies for detection, identification and early warning (e.g., Distributed acoustic sensing for monitoring third-party's intrusion, cognitive and combined frameworks for biometrics and video analytics, sensors for detection, identification and early warning).
- Technologies for joint cyber-physical security risk management and resilience modelling (e.g., cyber-physical risk and resilience modelling and management, gas network advanced modelling and fast dynamic simulation, risk-aware information to the population).
- Combined analytics for biometrics and video analytics.³⁰
- Provision of Risk-Awareness Information to the general population.³¹

Main Technological Outcomes of STOP-IT project:

The STOP-IT project has focused on the security and resilience of water management infrastructures. It has delivered an integrated platform with the following properties:

- Scalability i.e. scaling from small utilities to large ones.
- Adaptable based on various modules that address different needs, with expandability for future modules.
- Flexible as it allows water utility managers to decide how to use it, while being usable by experts, novices, and even non-technical staff.

The STOP-IT platform supports strategic/tactical planning, RT operational decision making and post-action assessment for the key parts of the water infrastructure. The STOP-IT platform integrates nine modular components containing a total of 27 tools, methods, services and/or platforms brought by

³⁰https://www.securegas-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/C3-Combined-analytics-for-biometrics-and-video-analytics_INNOV.pdf

³¹<https://www.securegas-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/D3-Risk-Aware-Information-to-the-population.pdf>

the STOP-IT partners. Table *Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-14* presents the modules of the STOP-IT platform, while Table *Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-15* provides an overview of the STOP-IT tools.

Table Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-14: STOP-IT platform modules

A/A	Module	Module Description	Level
1	Module 1	Risk Assessment and Treatment Framework	strategic/tactical
2	Module 2	Secure wireless sensor communications module	operational
3	Module 3	Toolbox of technologies for securing IT and SCADA	operational
4	Module 4	Toolbox of technologies for protecting against physical threats in CI	operational
5	Module 5	Cyber Threat Incident Sharing Service	operational
6	Module 6	Real-time anomaly detection system	operational
7	Module 7	Public warning system secure information exchange technologies	operational
8	Module 8	Reasoning Engine	operational / platform-integral part
9	Module 9	Enhanced Visualization Interface for the Water Utilities	operational / platform-integral part

Table Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-15: Overview of STOP-IT tools

A/A	Abbreviation	Tool Name	Module	Level
1	RIDB	Risk Identification Database	1	strategic/tactical
2	InfraRisk CP	InfraRisk for Cyber Physical threats	1	strategic/tactical
3	AVAT	Asset Vulnerability Assessment Tool	1	strategic/tactical
4	SP	Scenario Planner	1	strategic/tactical

A/A	Abbreviation	Tool Name	Module	Level
5	RAET	Risk Analysis and Evaluation Toolkit	1	strategic/tactical
6	RRMD	Risk Reduction Measures Database	1	strategic/tactical
7	TORC	Training for Operational Resilience	1	strategic/tactical
8	STP	Stress Testing Platform	1	strategic/tactical
9	FTE	Fault Tree Editor	8	strategic/tactical
10	KPItool	Key Performance Indicators tool	1	strategic/tactical
11	Jdet	Jammer Detector	2	operational
12	NTSA	Network Traffic Sensors and Analysers	3	operational
13	RSDP	Real-time sensor data protection	3	operational
14	WQSP	Optimisation Tool for Sensor Placement and Management	3	operational
15	FTCS	Fault-tolerant Control Strategies for Physical Anomalies affecting the SCADA system	4	operational
16	CVT	Computer Vision Tools	4	operational
17	FCAC	Fine-grained Cyber Access Control	4	operational
18	Smart-Locks	Access Control System using Electronic Locks	4	operational
19	HPD	Human Presence Detection using WiFi signals	4	operational
20	CTsS	Cyber Threat Sharing Service	5	operational

A/A	Abbreviation	Tool Name	Module	Level
21	RTAD	Real-Time Anomaly Detector	6	operational
22	XL-SIEM	Cross Layer Security Information and Event Management	6	operational
23	OPWS	Optimised Public Warning System	7	operational
24	REN	Reasoning Engine	8	Integral part of STOP-IT platform
25	EVI	Enhanced Visualisation Interface for the water utilities	9	Integral part of STOP-IT platform
26	RGIP	RISA GEN Integration Platform	9	Integral part of STOP-IT platform
27	IWM	Interoperability Water Middleware	9	Integral part of STOP-IT platform

2.4.3.2. Non-Technological

Apart from the scientific and technological development outcomes, the various project has produced non-technical assets, such as legal frameworks, policy guidelines and educational platforms. These assets play an important role in CIP through complementing the technological outcomes. Following paragraphs illustrates the main non-technological outcomes of selected projects.

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of Cybersane:

The project has produced the following non-technological outcomes:

- An Ethical and Privacy Social Common framework on security.
- Two different questionnaires for the socio-economic and techno-economic evaluation of the CyberSANE platform.
- A usability evaluation methodology in the context of effectiveness and convenience.
- A set of Best Practices and Policy Development Guidelines for Replicability and Wider Use.

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of DEFENDER:

The project has produced the following non-technological outcomes:

- The creation of a culture of security where trusted information exchange between trained employees and volunteers will complement cyber-physical protection, while preserving the privacy of the citizens involved.
- A Methodology for predicting and managing Critical Energy Infrastructure (CEI) risks: providing experiences, know-how and competences based on the adaption, integration, upscaling, deployment and validation of innovative technologies and operational blueprints and deploy them within an integrated yet adaptable methodological framework for CEI security for a better prediction and management of risks, supporting all the involved stakeholders to better act.

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of Digital Water City:

The project has produced the following non-technological outcomes:

- A Policy Brief.³²
- Training materials.³³

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of ENSURESEC:

The project has produced the following non-technological outcomes:

- A Robust Data protection policy
- An Enhanced deployment planning.
- Trainings for SMEs and clients/users of e-commerce infrastructures and transactions.

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of FINSEC:

The project has produced the following non-technological outcomes:

- Integrated Security Policies combining Cyber + Physical Security
- The Finsecurity.eu portal and the project's training academy.
- The FINSTIX data model, which defines scenarios and incident for physical/logical infrastructure. FINSTIX foster a standards-based approach to modelling cyber-physical threat intelligence scenarios and events.

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of InfraStress:

The project has produced the following non-technological outcomes:

- The concept of hybrid threat shall be further developed to accommodate other sectors than the ones already covered by the EU initiatives in this sense. The chemical sector is one of such domains needing explicit reference in the above-mentioned strategic initiatives.
- A piecemeal approach towards cybersecurity should be replaced with more granular and holistic initiatives aimed at paying sufficient attention to all potential targets of insecurity.
- SELP methodologies should be disseminated in order to promote a legal culture across similar security projects.
- Organizational learning STaff RIde Protocol.

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of PRAETORIAN:

The project has produced the following non-technological outcomes:

- An Ethical and Privacy Social Common framework on security.

³² <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/6eb837b2-54df-11ed-92ed-01aa75ed71a1>

³³ <https://www.digital-water.city/news/water-systems-cyber-physical-entities-trainin-secure-system/>

- The PRAETORIAN toolset that supports the security managers of ECIs in their decision making to anticipate and withstand potential cyber, physical or combined security threats to their own ECI and other interrelated ECIs that could have a severe impact on their performance and/or the security of the population in their vicinity. It also addresses how an attack or an incident in a specific ECI can jeopardise the regular operation of other neighbouring/interrelated ECIs and how to make all of them more resilient by predicting cascading effects and proposing a unified response among ECI assisting First Responder teams.

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of PRECINCT:

The project has produced the following non-technological outcomes:

- A PRECINCT Framework Specification for systematic CIs security and resilience management fulfilling industry requirements.
- Critical infrastructure interdependencies and cascading effects interdependency graphs to support intelligent reasoning both in gaming applications and the PRECINCT Digital Twins.
- Deeper knowledge of critical infrastructures and their interrelationships, which provides policy makers with a valid tool to direct policy choices.

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of RESISTO:

The project has produced the following non-technological outcomes:

- Operational support to security teams for risk evaluation about attack priorities and intervention policies.
- A means of objective representation of resilience indicators that applies to most telecommunication operators.
- A liability framework: a system that models, simulates cascading effects and recommends mitigation actions should have clear policies that are reliable when the results cause damages and harm.

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of SAFECARE:

The project has produced the following non-technological outcomes:

- Guidance on the Importance of Incident Notification Mechanisms.
- Guidance on the Importance of NIS Directive.
- Guidance on the Importance of ECI Directive.

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of SAFETY4RAILS:

The project has produced the following non-technological outcomes:

- Improvement of both internal and external communications, in a sector where crisis management involves a large number of stakeholders.
- Closer cooperation with authorities is a key element of crisis and incident management, via, for instance, operation information exchanges facilitated by dedicated systems, coordination of measures and actions implementation, joint trainings, harmonisation of standard operation procedures.
- A Methodology for resilience assessment for rail infrastructure considering cyber-physical threats.³⁴
- The Modelling Cyber-Risk in an Economic Perspective [19].³⁵

³⁴ https://safety4rails.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/CPS4CIP_2022_paper_8330.pdf

³⁵ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9527994>

- Resilience Management Concept for Railways and Metro Cyber-Physical Systems.³⁶

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of SATIE:

The project has produced the following non-technological outcomes:

- Best practices for airport security standards.³⁷
- Standardization of EU project outcomes, advanced risk assessment, market analysis.

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of Sauron:

The project has produced an Ethical and Privacy Social Common framework on security.

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of SecureGas:

The project has produced the following non-technological outcomes:

- Processes to follow in case of security-related emergency situations among CI operators, private entities and public authorities.
- Advanced Risk analysis approach toward a Resilience-Based Management of Gas Assets and Infrastructures: a systemic (multi-hazards, multi-threats) security risk and resilience management approaches, including the combination of physical and cyber threats, their interconnections, cascading effects.
- A Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) to asset the benefits and impact of SecureGas in the three Business Cases.
- SecureGas White paper “Lessons learnt and recommendations for cyber-physical resilience of European Gas Critical Infrastructure”.
- Two very important recommendations:
 - Member State shall conduct a Resilience Assessment of Critical Entities at National Level in compliance with CER and NIS2 proposal directive for the purposes of enhancing the overall resilience of the key energy critical infrastructure.
 - Each Member State shall conduct large-scale vulnerability assessment and long-term risk assessment, taking into account cross-border and cross-sectoral interdependencies and physical-cyber and Hybrid Threats.

Main Non-Technological Outcomes of STOP-IT:

The project has produced the following non-technological outcomes:

- A Societal Impact Assessment of STOP-IT, based on relevant Deliverables and a set of semi-structured interviews with the Frontrunner utilities (D1.4 – Societal Impact Assessment, WP1, PU).³⁸
- An overview of the activities carried out in the Communities of Practice (CoPs) within the STOP-IT project, together with summarizing the feedback of the participants and facilitators, and providing recommendations for future CoP activities (D2.2 – Annual technical and policy brief based on the results of each CoP, WP2, PU).³⁹

³⁶ <https://www.theseus.fi/handle/10024/504606>

³⁷ https://satie-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/SATIE_D7.3_Best-practices-for-updating-airport-security-standard-and-policies_U_v1.0_compressed-1.pdf

³⁸ <https://stop-it-project.eu/download/societal-impact-report-d1-4/>

³⁹ <https://stop-it-project.eu/download/annual-technical-and-policy-brief-based-on-the-results-of-each-cop-d2-2/>

- Best practice guidelines for Communities of Practice (CoPs) in water infrastructure and lessons for future activities beyond the STOP-IT project (D2.3 – Best practice guidelines for CoPs in Water Infrastructure protection, WP2, EU-RES).
- A list of training materials and products developed by the project for each one of the defined user profiles (D8.2 – Training and knowledge transfer material and products, WP8, PU). The comprehensive list of training material is available at ⁴⁰.
- Identification of appropriate actions needed to ensure continuity of the training courses and services beyond the project duration (D8.4 – Continuity plan for the training courses and services, WP8, PU).⁴¹ This report has been further extended in the Digital Water City Project.⁴²

2.5. Stakeholders' Feedback on CIP Trends, Capabilities and Standards

2.5.1. The Role of Stakeholders' Feedback in EU-CIP-ANALYSIS

EU-CIP-ANALYSIS is related to the information collection, monitoring, curation, and analysis pillar of the project. It will collect, process, and provide rich, accurate, credible, up-to-date, and easily accessible information about research outcomes, technologies, standards and policies for resilient infrastructures. The main **challenge** in the current context is to deal with the **fragmentation of information** regarding research outcomes, research projects, technologies, policies, and standards for resilient infrastructures. The main problem is that information related to these topics is often scattered across various sources and locations, making it difficult for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners to access and utilize this information effectively. This fragmentation of information can result in duplication of research efforts, gaps in knowledge, and inconsistencies in policy and practice. It can also make it difficult for practitioners to identify best practices and emerging technologies for building resilient infrastructure systems.

The **EU-CIP approach** is to establish a data collection, information monitoring and analysis methodology and infrastructure, which will continually collect, analyse, curate, extract and present information and insights about resilient infrastructures. EU-CIP approach starts with the design of a methodology and infrastructure for data collection, information monitoring and analysis is essential for continually collecting, analysing, curating, extracting, and presenting information and insights about resilient infrastructures. By implementing such a system, it is possible to stay up to date on the latest research findings, emerging technologies, and best practices in the field, enabling them to make informed decisions about infrastructure planning and management.

Some key steps for designing such a system are presented in Figure *Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.*-7:

Figure *Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.*-7: EU-CIP methodological approach

⁴⁰ <https://stop-it-project.eu/results-and-downloads/transfer-training-activities/>

⁴¹ <https://stop-it-project.eu/results/training-material-for-risk-officers-and-modellers/#toggle-id-18>

⁴² <https://www.digital-water.city/news/water-systems-cyber-physical-entities-trainin-secure-system/>

Regarding the **Step 2: Develop data collection procedures**, once the relevant sources have been identified, data and information collection procedures need to be developed to automate the process of data collection from various sources.

A variety of information collection modalities will be considered in addition to desk research, including **interviews with relevant stakeholders** (Internal Consultation with Relevant Stakeholders) inside the consortium, feedback based on questionnaires, as well as secondary research based on proper curation of the collected data. EU-CIP have planned regular consultation activities with the consortium members, which represent different CIP/CIR stakeholders in a variety of sectors. To this end, internal consultation and feedback collection mechanisms have been developed. Desk research has been complemented with findings and information from regular consultations with internal stakeholders. To support feedback collection from such consultations, an information collection form has been provided in Annex I. Key findings from the stakeholders' consultation process are integrated in this report. Subsequent versions of this report will include updated information from surveys and discussions with internal stakeholders', while at the same time integrating feedback from external stakeholders i.e., third party experts beyond the consortium organizations. In this direction, EU-CIP has already published information about its 1st Open Call for engaging external experts in stakeholders' consultations and CIP information analysis.

2.5.2. Preliminary Insights on Main Capability Needs

2.5.2.1. General Sector Agnostic Capability Needs

EU-CIP consortium members have identified the following CIP capabilities that are not adequately supported and covered by existing solutions:

- **C1 - Enhanced adaptability:** There is a need to enhance **adaptability** to new threats, as the novel and sometimes asymmetric threats against CIs happen with higher frequency than ever before.
- **C2 - Reduced Response Times:** EU-CIP experts identified a need for increasing the speed of **response** as a means of coping with highly volatile environments and minimize the costs of potential damage.
- **C3 - Increased Transparency:** In an era where complex threats are handled by sophisticated technologies, there is a need for improving transparency of the solution for the stakeholders.
- **C4 - Improved Detection Capabilities:** Improved **detection** over current state of the art based on solutions that: (i) Address novel threats like hybrid threats combining cyber security and physical security aspects); (ii) Provide improved analytics capabilities of detection & response tools that account for the rapid shifting in the IoT and 5G spaces, while offering improved informed decision making. Overall, there is a need for advanced prevention and detection systems against digital and physical attacks, which must be integrated within powerful monitoring and alert systems. These systems must also address ICS/OT threat detection and prevention, along with industry related threat intelligence information sharing and advanced risk analytics.
- **C5 - Improved risk and impact assessment capabilities** to address novel integrated, hybrid and asymmetric threats against a broad range of cyber and physical assets.
- **C6 - Better integration of Telco Security tools with Information Security Management tools.** This integration should strive to avoid existing silos and fragmentation in security systems and capabilities.

- **C7 – Solutions addressing cascading effects between different entities and states.** Such solutions must help preventing disruptions on supply chain services towards ensuring the continuity of business operations across different value chains.
 - **C8 - Transformation of proactive and adaptive protection tools and methods to incorporate real-time functionalities.** Such functionalities will boost the protection and resilience of CI through improved collection and analysis of real-time data in the light of the ever evolving and dynamically changing threat landscape.
 - **C9 – Better Exploitation of information from critical sensors towards augmented situation awareness.** Input from critical sensors (e.g., cameras, human presence, luminosity, weather/environment parameters) must be better integrated and exploited within CIP systems towards improving situation awareness (e.g., about security personnel positions and CI assets state). The latter must be combined with proper revisions to security and emergency management processes.
 - **C10 – Risk prediction and anticipation,** leading to earlier detection of threats and subsequently enhancing resilience, monitoring, patrolling, decision support, and event management applications.
 - **C11 – Training, Reskilling and Upskilling.** There is a need for developing relevant skills and competences in collaboration with the research and the academic community. Prominent examples of the required skills development, include cybersecurity and cyber-resilience trainings.
- Beyond the above-listed general capabilities that are applicable to all CIP sectors, the capabilities needed for critical infrastructure sectors vary depending on the specific sector. EU-CIP partners have expertise in different sectors and have identified capabilities needs linked to specific sectors.

2.5.2.2. Transport Sector

The following capabilities needs are envisaged as being very important for the transport sector:

- The development of dataspace covering all stakeholders and enabling increased situation awareness of both threats and cascading effects.
- Coordinated response management systems to security events.
- Solutions providing fast and correct responses to issues in order to ensure the high availability need of certain transport ecosystems (e.g., of the aerospace ecosystem).

2.5.2.3. Railway Sector

A crucial part of the CIP capabilities of the railway infrastructures concerns the IT security of the systems that support the railway infrastructure. In fact, it is necessary to continuously invest in updating these security systems as they are responsible for protecting the digital ecosystem from the risk of malicious infiltrations both from inside and outside, which can endanger the normal functioning of the railway infrastructure.

Further aspects that represent potential criticalities for the railway infrastructure are extreme environmental events, characterized by an ever-greater unpredictability and destructive capacity. The latter are exacerbated by climate change phenomena such as floods, landslides, heavy snowfalls, etc.

2.5.2.4. Water Sector

The Water sector can greatly benefit from the following capabilities:

- IT-OT integration.
- CIP awareness and training.
- Development of integrated environments for safety and security policies.

2.5.2.5. Finance Sector

CIP capabilities in the finance sector must evolve in the light of the rapid digitization of the financial services infrastructure. Hence, capabilities for strong cybersecurity, fraud detection and cyber threat intelligence are required.

2.5.2.6. Manufacturing and Industrial Sectors

CIP capabilities for industrial environments must emphasize on device security and trust, as well as on solutions for securing the cloud/edge computing continuum. These are some of the main requirements of industrial CIP operators when it comes to securing their production plants and their industrial operations.

2.5.2.7. Energy sector

Relevant capabilities involve the development and use of security standards for physical protection. Moreover, in the energy sector there is a need to prioritize capabilities that increase resilience of CIs.

2.5.3. Preliminary Insights on Capability Gaps

2.5.3.1. General Sector Agnostic Capability Gaps

The EU-CIP consortium members have also identified the following list of preliminary Capability Gaps (CG), which are partly linked to the above listed needs:

- **CG1 - Poor Automation:** There is currently poor automation when it comes to achieving fast detection, protection and recovery from cyber-attacks. Specifically, there is a gap in closing the cybersecurity automation loop to automatically verify, diagnose, rectify, monitor, measure, and improve security controls. This gap is very evident when it comes to supporting heterogeneous technology and configurations in a systematic and justifiable manner.
- **CG2 – Lack of proper control of Interconnectedness:** CI operators are not currently offered with strong control over interconnected assets and their dependencies. This makes it difficult to implement a holistic CIP approach that considers the dependencies of the various assets, as well as related cascading effects.

- **CG3 – Poor Alignment of Resilience Indicators:** Currently CI operators deal with a host of resilience indicators, which are not aligned and, in several cases, diverse and non-compatible. This hinders the implementation of a structured CIR approach.
- **CG4 – Lack of agreed Standards-based stress-testing procedures:** Along with poor alignment of indicators, there is also a lack of agreed stress-testing procedures that could foster the implementation of structured, standards-based CIR approaches.
- **CG5 – Problems with the classification of IoT Devices:** In recent years there is a proliferation of IoT devices in Cis. However, the identification and classification of IoT-based assets is lagging behind the output of the suppliers and does not scale to account for the increased diversity and complexity of the various classes of IoT devices.
- **CG6 – Scalability in the Mitigation of Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks:** DDoS attack mitigation is not scaling optimal given the increase in the bandwidth that is nowadays available to end-users (e.g., multi-gigabit per second connectivity is now widely available to SMEs).
- **CG7 – Development and Deployment of AI-based systems:** Despite recent advances in AI systems and technologies, the potential of AI in CIP/CIR solutions remains underexploited. Moreover, there is still poor awareness about AI capabilities within employees and CIP/CIR vendors. Likewise, existing solutions cannot deal effectively with AI-powered cyberattacks based on new adaptive AI technologies.
- **CG8 – Lack of Holistic Security Management Systems:** There is a lack of holistic security management solutions, which are operationally applicable and do not need to be customised from scratch. Furthermore, there is a lack of solutions that are uniform and operations across the large number of different stakeholders.
- **CG9 – Gaps in Emergency Management Processes:** There are significant gaps in standardised processes in cases of emergencies. For instance, there is a lack of universally agreed processes regarding the communication with external entities for emergency handling and with public authorities regarding security/safety incidents related communications.
- **CG10 – Inability to cope with dynamically evolving threats:** There is a lack of dynamic and intelligent solutions that can deal with the ever evolving and dynamically changing threats proactively and adaptively. Adaptive, AI-based solutions could provide the required intelligence, yet they are still not widely developed and used in the CIP/CIR domain.
- **CG11 – Poor Awareness about modern CIP/CIR challenges:** There is a generally a lack of awareness regarding contemporary CIP/CIR requirements, such as awareness about cascading events, preparedness against new natural and anthropic risks, and complex cyber resilience issues.

Beyond the above-listed general capabilities gaps that are applicable to all CIP sectors, EU-CIP partners have expertise in different sectors and have identified capabilities gaps linked to specific sectors.

2.5.3.2. Air-transport Sector

Airports rely mostly on OT systems, which limits the capabilities of the existing technologies in terms of incident detection and response. Existing CIP/CIR solutions for the aerospace sector are generally limited in terms of the context considered. For example, some solutions focus only on the apparent threats without considering also the big picture and weak signals coming from hybrid threats and possible cascading effects. Likewise, there is a lack of responsible organisations to set up and manage

data spaces for CIP/CIR in the sectors. Moreover, there is quite low maturity in advanced coordinated decision-making solutions.

2.5.3.3. Railway Sector

Nowadays, the railway sector lacks exhaustive elements to monitor environmental events such as, for example, an efficient system for detecting ground movement in the event of a landslide or detection of the amount of rain to predict any flooding of railway sections. A further element is the communication systems of the railways (e.g., in Italy), which requires a general improvement of tools and supporting infrastructures to ameliorate the communication between railways operators and to strengthen security against intrusions from outside the organization.

2.5.3.4. Finance Sector

CIP/CIR solutions for the finance sector come with quite limited Intelligence. For instance, they operate based on fixed rules and do not exploit ML systems and AI-based automations. Furthermore, CIP/CIR solutions do not address security challenges of the financial supply chain, such as information sharing challenges. Moreover, CIP/CIR solutions must cope with human factor challenges (e.g., lack of security awareness and adherence to security policies).

2.5.3.5. Water Sector

The CG of the water sector, including poor IT-OT integration due to technical challenges, but also due to: (i) Siloed risk management systems and (ii) Lack of professional profiles with proper skillset, including a lack of proper awareness and competences.

2.5.3.6. Manufacturing Sector

CIP/CIR capabilities in the manufacturing sector must be improved to provide better support for edge devices security and to address supply chain security challenges. Furthermore, they must consider cybersecurity and integrated IT/OT security to address digital transformation challenges.

2.5.3.7. Energy Sector

One of the capability gaps that are specific to the energy sector is the lack of state authority for control of CIP, as well as of a pen-test institution for all areas of security.

2.5.3.8. Higher Education and R&D Sectors

Relevant capability gaps for this sector include the need for improved situational awareness and better support for security-related decision-making and resilience management. Moreover, most cybersecurity systems are based on legacy technologies and unable to cope with modern challenges.

2.5.4. Preliminary Insights about Trends, Standards and State of the Art Technologies that Address Capability Gaps

The technologies and tools that can help close gaps in CIP/CIR can help prevent, detect, and mitigate potential threats to CIs, such as cyber-attacks, physical attacks, and natural disasters. For example, advanced cybersecurity technologies can help detecting and preventing cyber-attacks on CIs, while physical security technologies can help deter and detect physical attacks. Additionally, technologies such as predictive analytics and machine learning can help identifying potential vulnerabilities and risks to critical infrastructure systems, towards enabling proactive mitigation measures. The implementation of state-of-the-art technologies and tools can boost the resilience and continuity of critical infrastructure systems, protecting society from the potentially devastating consequences of their disruption or destruction.

Figure Errore. **Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-8 illustrates the findings of the EU-CIP survey about the technologies that could help at alleviating existing capability gaps. In-line with the identified gaps technologies like cyber-physical threat intelligence, security risk assessment and modelling of cascading effects were perceived as the most promising for mitigating the list gaps. This is because the implementation of integrated security approaches and the handling of cascading effects were perceived as the some of the key capabilities that are currently missing for CIP/CIR systems.

Adaptive threat hunting	9
Anomaly Detection	13
Biometric Authentication	1
Blockchain/DLT Technology	3
Closed Circuit Television Systems	4
Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence	17
Cybersecurity Tools	12
Data Loss Prevention Technology	8
Digital twins	13
Disinformation Management	6
End-Point Protection	5
Image Analysis	5
Impact assessment tools	14
Machine Learning – Pattern Det...	10
Modelling of cascading effects a...	12
Pentesting	9
Security Information and Event ...	7
Security Risk Assessment	16
Social Media Analysis	4
Unmanned Aerial Vehicles	5
Visual Scene Analysis	3
Sandboxes	1
Social Graph Analysis	2
Surveillance Systems	7
Malware Detection	11
Ransomware	7
5G Communications – Internet ...	8
Altro	4

Figure **Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-8**: State of the Art Technologies and Tools covering the current gaps

Furthermore, Figure **Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-9** illustrates some of the trending CIP/CIR technologies according to the internal survey of the project and the feedback of EU-CIP members. The results of the trends survey are in-line with the above-listed technologies. Specifically, cyber-physical threat intelligence represents one of the most important trends followed by collaborative threat intelligence and predictive security.

Adaptive Threat Hunting	6
Autonomous adaptive security	8
Automation using Artificial Intell...	9
Collaborative Threat Intelligence	14
Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligen...	17
Federated Attack Libraries	4
Federated Security Knowledge B...	5
Fighting misinformation	6
Predictive Security	14
Threat anticipation	13
Altro	3

Figure **Errore**. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-9: Important trends IN CIP/CIR domain

2.5.5. CIP/CIR Standards Relevant to EU-CIP

The main calling of the relevant ISO standards (ISO 31000 series and 223xx series, see Figure **Errore**. *Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-10*) is to provide universal, yet meaningful guidance on developing new competencies and business models to create relevant and realistic recommendations in an ever-changing uncertain world of CIP/CIR. Risk and resilience are part of almost every strategic decision in in CIP/CIR management, but often burdened by complex and uncertain issues: a more adaptive and comprehensive policy, frameworks and are needed for this, and some have been developed and being developed under ISO, CEN and NSBs umbrellas (ISO – International Standardization Organization, CEN – Committee for European Norms, NSBs – National Standardization Bodies).

In the ISO realm, the root standard is the ISO 31000, dealing with risk is part of governance and leadership. These considerations are at the heart of ISO 31000, Risk management – Guidelines, which delivers a clearer, shorter and more concise guide that will help organizations use risk management principles to improve planning and make better decisions.

Figure **Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-10: Managing risk and resilience under the umbrella of ISO

In the standard, risk is defined as the “effect of uncertainty on objectives”, which focuses on the effect of incomplete knowledge of events or circumstances on an organization’s decision-making. This requires a change in the traditional understanding of risk, forcing organizations to tailor risk management to their needs and objectives – a key benefit of the standard. The framework supports all activities, including decision making across all levels of the organization. The ISO 31000 framework and its processes should be integrated with governance, strategy and management systems to ensure consistency and the effectiveness of management control across all areas of the organization. This includes strategy and planning, organizational resilience, IT, corporate governance, human resources, compliance, quality, health and safety, business continuity, crisis management and security. All of which are relevant to responding to a pandemic. Resilience is built on understanding current and emerging risk and building the adaptive and responsive elements of the organization to deal with the risk one knows and anticipate, through a resilience strategy to address both the known and unknown “Known” and the known and unknown “Unknown”. The application is supported by the methodologies available in IEC/ISO 31010 Risk Management – Risk assessment techniques, providing guidance on the selection and application of techniques for assessing risk in a wide range of situations.

With the new ISO 31050, currently under development (the DTS is currently in the process of approval as an ISO Technical Specification), the decision makers will be better equipped to manage both known (ISO 31000) and emerging risks. To this aim, the 31050 delivers structured context (e.g., definitions, drivers, metrics, etc.), emerging risk management framework, the procedure, the guidance for common format(s) for interoperability and indicators. It will also deliver emerging risk application examples in the informative annexes of the standard. The recommendations of the standard should facilitate best practices, enhance resilience, promote agility, assist transformation, deliver insight, ensure foresight, establish value and integrate resources – also for enhancing resilience of critical infrastructures. The standard is monitored by the ISO Technical Committees TC262 and TC292.

Other relevant standards are being collected and structured in the EU-CIP Observatory, currently comprising the following RESILIENCE standards (developed and under development) listed in Annex III. The project will consider joining as the project in liaison the WG dealing with the development ISO/WD 22372 Security and resilience – Resilient Infrastructure – Guidelines. The partner EU-VRI will undertake the respective steps on behalf of the project.

Figure **Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-11 illustrates how the EU-CIP partners graded various standards in-terms of their importance for CIP/CIR. Mainstream cybersecurity standards (notably the standards of the 27000 family) stand out in terms of popularity. Other ISO standards (e.g., ISO/TC 262 for risk management) follow in popularity.

ISO/TC 292 Security and Resilien...	6
ISO 28000 series	5
ISO 28000:2022 S	3
ISO 28002:2011	2
ISO 22000 series: ISO 22301:201...	4
Under development: ISO/AWI 8...	1
ISO/TC 262 Risk management	5
Under development: ISO/CD TS ...	1
ISO / IEC: ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27 : I...	3
ISO 27000 family of standards: I...	15
Under development: ISO/IEC DI...	1
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 30	1
Under development: ISO/IEC CD...	0
Under development: ISO/IEC W...	1
ISA/IEC	2
IEC 62443 Industrial communica...	4
IEC 61850: ISO/PWI 6367	2
CEN: CEN/CLC/WS 018 ;; CWA 1...	2
Other standards-related publica...	8
Altro	4

Figure *Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.*-11: Notable CIP/CIR Standards

2.5.6. Preliminary Insights on Education and Training Gaps

2.5.6.1. Training Topics of Interest

As already outlined, education, upskilling and reskilling of CI operators' employees is a key for the deployment and operation of effective CIP/CIR solutions. To this end, EU-CIP is developing training and skills development resources (activity: Innovation Management and Virtualized Solutions Validation Services). The internal stakeholders survey of the project took however the opportunity to solicit feedback about the training and skills gaps in CIP/CIR. Specifically, the survey highlighted the need to train stakeholders based on the end-users' information and systems criticality access level in a realistic training environment. Moreover, it was deduced that state of the art cybersecurity training curricula for security practitioners must be adapted to CIP/CIR requirements and industry needs.

Main topics of interest include trainings on:

- (i) Cutting-edge infrastructures and technologies.
- (ii) Modern Asymmetric Threats.
- (iii) Different types of Artificial Intelligence and their role in security.
- (iv) Curricula that combine digital and physical security risks.
- (v) Integration and interconnection of diverse systems in CI facilities, including OT/IT integration.
- (vi) Risk assessment and preparedness based on a good balance between risks and resilience.
- (vii) Applied resilience, including support for incidents caused by unexpected events.
- (viii) New kinds of skills relating to digitalization and high-tech society.
- (ix) CIP security management, leadership and governance skills, including cyber resilience best practices and cyber diplomacy.
- (x) Capacity to anticipate, prepare for, and respond to incidents and attacks.
- (xi) Skills for federated activities and cooperation in regional-national-EU-global federations.
- (xii) Cyber security skills.
- (xiii) Hybrid security skills (e.g., leveraging outcomes of EU-HYBNET), including hybrid impact on individuals and citizen's responsibility.
- (xiv) Crisis communication skills, including skills against infodemic and crisis impacting, human factors, digital literacy, psychotherapy and management of fear and mental pressures.
- (xv) Training on understanding interdependencies and improvement strategies for critical infrastructures.

The above-listed training needs will be considered in the specification and implementation of the training and skills development activities of the project (Innovation Management and Virtualized Solutions Validation Services).

2.5.6.2. CIP/CIR Training and Upskilling Best Practices

In terms of training and skills development activities, the EU-CIP partners have also outlined the following best practices:

- A) A one-size-fits-all training solution is not the right path. Tailored and specialized training is needed depending on the needs of the industry as a whole and of the specific end-users' requirements for reskilling and upskilling. Furthermore, training activities must be customized to different profiles of CI workers. For instance, risk managers must be trained on IT/OT risk management integration. Likewise, people in charge of emergency management and Real Time Communications (RTC) processes must be trained on the operation and use of CIP systems and technologies.
- B) Mastering critical infrastructure protection and resilience requires the entire lifecycle and at several levels from strategy to implementation and operations. Specifically:

- At the strategy level there is a need to do more training of dynamic risk assessment, definition of a governance structure and adaptive monitoring tools.
 - At the implementation level integration of security, data protection and resilience at all stages (development, deployment, testing, documentation, etc.).
 - At the operations level protection of systems: securing the means of communication, regular audits, supervisions, continuous threat hunting and anticipation.
- C) It is important to create awareness about CIP requirements at the highest management level of critical infrastructure operations. Senior management backing and support is a key success factor for most CIP-related training and skills development activities.

There is a need for reinforcing the digital literacy and expertise of CI workers. Therefore, there is a need for more extensive training on IT and cybersecurity. Likewise, it is important to improve the cyber skills of non-ICT professionals in various CI sectors (e.g., doctors and nurses in healthcare, engineers and technicians in industrial sectors).

3. EU-CIP Analysis Outlook: Reports and Whitepapers

The EU-CIP analysis reports, along with other knowledge assets (e.g. directories of policies and standards, a directory of CIP/CIR technologies and research outcomes, a directory of research and innovation projects, training materials, white papers) will be integrated in a Knowledge-Hub. The latter will provide a single point of access for all the knowledge that will be produced in EU-CIP. It will facilitate stakeholders' access to information, which will support their on-line collaboration.

The findings of the desk research and the information from the consultations will be analysed, curated, and structured in reports and knowledge assets, which will be customized and disseminated to relevant stakeholders. The project will periodically produce the reports asked for in the call. With this, EU-CIP will provide tangible values to stakeholders and help them accomplish their CIP/CIR related tasks. The extraction of the reports will be facilitated by the structuring of knowledge in the FAIR data observatory, as well as by the integration of stakeholders' domain knowledge through the Knowledge Hub.

3.1. Outlook of Value-Added Reports to the European Commission

This section provides insights on added-value information, foresight and reports that the project intends to produce as part of subsequent versions of the present report. Following paragraphs provide an outlook of the five basic reports (Report1-Report5) that will be delivered to the EC, including:

1. Aggregated and consolidated view of the capability needs and gaps in CIP/CIR (Report 1).
2. Aggregated and consolidated view of the state-of-the-art technologies, techniques, methods and tools (Report 2).
3. Aggregated and consolidated view of outcomes, future trends, lessons learnt, and best practices derived from past and current security research projects (Report 3).
4. Common and updated map of opportunities and constraints for the exploitation of EU security research and innovation projects (Report 4).
5. Areas for Standardization and Certification (Report 5).

Section 2 provides already initial information that could serve as a starting point for producing these reports. For instance, the analysis of the various projects and their important outcomes provides a sound basis for initiating the production of Report 3.

3.1.1. Aggregated and Consolidated View of the Capability Needs and Gaps in CIP/CIR (Report 1)

This report will perform a gap analysis to existing CIP/CIR capabilities in the various sectors. As a first step, the report will outline the most recent challenges faced by critical infrastructures operators, including challenges faced by changes in the European and global context of critical infrastructures (e.g., challenges stemming from the proliferation of disinformation and challenges associated with large scale disruptions of value chains). Accordingly, it will identify the limitations of existing CIP/CIR solutions that hinder them from addressing these challenges.

The work of the previous section will be a starting point for identifying current CIP/CIR capabilities towards performing the gap analysis.

3.1.2. Aggregated and Consolidated View of the State-of-the-Art Technologies, Techniques, Methods and Tools (Report 2)

Aggregated and consolidated view of the state-of-the-art technologies, techniques, methods and tools that can contribute to fill the identified capability gaps.

This report will provide a consolidated view of the main CIP/CIR technologies, techniques, methods and tools, starting from the technologies listed in the previous section. The consolidation will present the main CIP/CIR applications / solutions that are enabled by these technologies. The various solutions will be analysed as a whole and per sector of relevance.

3.1.3. Aggregated and Consolidated View of Outcomes (Report 3)

This report will provide an aggregated and consolidated view of outcomes (including on technological, industrial, legal and ethical issues), future trends, lessons learnt, and best practices derived from past and current security research projects. The information presented in Section 2 will serve as a starting point. Project outcomes will be accordingly segmented and presented according to the following categories:

- Technological outcomes such as technological solutions.
- Industrial outcomes such as integrated security solutions for critical assets in different industries.
- Legal and ethical outcomes, such as ethical frameworks and recommendations.

3.1.4. Common and Updated Map of Opportunities and Constraints for the Exploitation of EU Security Research and Innovation Projects (Report R4)

A Common and updated map of opportunities and constraints for the exploitation of EU security research and innovation projects, with special focus on industrialisation, commercialisation, adoption, and deployment of innovative solutions in response to common capability gaps (Report R4).

3.1.5. Areas for Standardization and Certification (Report 5)

EU-CIP will produce a common and updated map of areas requiring standardised solutions and/or certification schemes to foster innovation uptake and market creation. The CIP/CIR areas (e.g., risk assessment, cyber-physical threat intelligence) where standards must be followed will be identified. In cases where existing standards can be used, these standards will be outlined. Likewise, in cases where there is a lack of appropriate standards, the project will analyse the standardization gap and will provide recommendations for pre-normative standardization activities.

3.2. Outlook of Roadmaps

3.2.1. CIP/CIR Roadmap Development Concept

The main starting points for the definition of the EU-CIP CIP/CIR roadmap are defined by the need to well align:

1. Policies
2. Research & innovation (R&I)
3. Standards
4. Go-to-market strategies and measures (G2M).

In addition, each of this area has to be well-aligned with the roadmaps (primarily the EU roadmaps) developed/existing, under development or yet-to be developed in the areas such as:

- Cybersecurity
- Resilience
- Critical infrastructures in the areas such as energy, environment, transportation, health, water, etc.

In particular, the strategic roadmaps such as the “European Green Deal – Striving to be the first climate-neutral continent”⁴³, will be:

- taken into account, and

⁴³ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

- aligned with the EU-CIP CIP/CIR roadmap, e.g., in terms of structure and time horizons (2050), in order to have best possible compatibility.

The above “related roadmaps” and the permanent monitoring of:

- Stakeholders’ needs
- Market trends and
- Societal transformation.

will provide the natural context of the work in the EU-CIP project.

Thus, the EU-CIP roadmap is envisaged as a “roadmap-of-4-roadmaps”, dynamically synchronized with the context, i.e., being a living document, possibly remaining as such also beyond the project (Figure **Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-12).

Figure **Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-12: EU-CIP Roadmap creation methodology

3.2.2. Structure of the CIP/CIR Roadmap and the 4 Sub-Roadmaps

The preliminary envisaged structure of the roadmap is:

Executive summary

1. PART 1: Procedural issues and consultation of interested parties
 - 1.1. Organization and timing
 - 1.2. Consultation and expertise

-
- A complex network diagram with numerous nodes and connecting lines, rendered in shades of blue and grey, serves as a background for the document. The nodes are of varying sizes and are interconnected by thin lines, creating a dense web of connections.
- 1.3. Opinion of the IAB
 2. PART 2: Problem definition
 - 2.1. Context: EU, national, regional, international
 - 2.2. Main problems to be tackled
 - 2.3. Underlying drivers and barriers
 - 2.4. Forecast if no action
 - 2.5. Impacts of no action
 3. PART 3: Objectives
 - 3.1. Highlights
 - 3.2. General objective, key figures, expected benefits
 - 3.3. Specific objectives, key figures, expected benefits
 - 3.4. Consistency with other (European) policies
 4. PART 4: Scenarios
 - 4.1. Assumptions
 - 4.2. Reference scenarios
 - 4.3. Methodology
 - 4.4. Options
 - 4.5. Impacts of the selected scenarios
 - 4.5.1. Environmental impacts
 - 4.5.2. Economic impacts
 - 4.5.3. Social impacts
 - 4.6. Indicators
 - 4.7. Sensitivity analysis
 - 4.8. Interconnectedness analysis
 5. PART 6: Proposing the options
 - 5.1. Implementation plan
 - 5.2. Priorities and timing of actions
 - 5.3. Monitoring and evaluation
 6. Conclusions

References

Annexes

(e.g., overall system costs, competitiveness and other socio-economic impacts)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

3.3. Outlook of EU-CIP White papers

3.3.1. Sectorial White papers

Following paragraphs provides a brief overview of White Papers that will be considered and produced by EU-CIP in different sectors of Critical Infrastructure. Specifically, following editions of the “Roadmaps, White Papers and Value-Added Reports” will provide additional papers which are based and will cumulate on the continuous research outcomes.

3.3.1.1. Telecommunications

The telecommunication sector comprises the companies that make communication possible on a global scale, whether through the phone or the Internet, or over airwaves or cables. These companies create the infrastructure that allows data in words, audio, or video to be sent anywhere in the world.

The resilience of the telecommunications providers is of utmost importance at both EU-level and Global Level, as the services and infrastructure provided by ‘Telcos’ are essential to the security and wellbeing of citizens. Furthermore, the cascading effects of the various threats affecting the telecommunications sector companies, can directly and immediately disrupt the infrastructures and services of other, interconnected critical infrastructures providers and / or essential services providers.

Among the principal threats affecting the resilience of the Telco companies, hybrid threats (I.e. - physical and cyber threats targeting connected infrastructure) are of clear importance, as it can affect multiple targets, across the various layers, components and systems used by services providers. Examples of such threats are (not limited to) - Intentional or accidental fibre optics severing, disruption of power delivery to network stations, acts of terrorism manifested through kinetic attacks to physical network assets, such as Base-Stations, data cabling, power cabling, secure access and threats in the cyber-domain such as Distributed Denial of Service Attacks, Insider Threats – Unauthorized Access, Data Exfiltration, Ransomware etc.

A hybrid threat scenario, during which a physical attack is concurrently run with a cyber-attack can affect the availability and/or integrity of the services provided, to a large degree, and correspondingly can affect interconnected infrastructures, providing services to other critical or essential services providers, across sectors such as Power, Water and Gas, Transportation, PPDR.

Table **Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-16 lists a subset of notable papers of the existing scientific literature on the resilience of the Telco Sector.

*Table **Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.**-16: Scientific Literature and Whitepapers for CIP/CIR in Telecommunications*

Scientific Papers and Whitepapers on CIP/CIR for Telecommunications Infrastructures

Cox, L.A.T. (2009). Making Telecommunications Networks Resilient against Terrorist Attacks. In: Bier, V.M., Azaiez, M.N. (eds) Game Theoretic Risk Analysis of Security

Scientific Papers and Whitepapers on CIP/CIR for Telecommunications Infrastructures

Threats. International Series in Operations Research & Management Science, vol 128. Springer, Boston, MA. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-87767-9_8

Onyema, E.M., Dinar, A.E., Ghouali, S., Merabet, B., Merzougui, R., Feham, M. (2022). Cyber Threats, Attack Strategy, and Ethical Hacking in Telecommunications Systems. In: Kaiwartya, O., Kaushik, K., Gupta, S.K., Mishra, A., Kumar, M. (eds) Security and Privacy in Cyberspace. Blockchain Technologies. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-1960-2_2

Onyema, E.M., Dinar, A.E., Ghouali, S., Merabet, B., Merzougui, R., Feham, M. (2022). Cyber Threats, Attack Strategy, and Ethical Hacking in Telecommunications Systems. In: Kaiwartya, O., Kaushik, K., Gupta, S.K., Mishra, A., Kumar, M. (eds) Security and Privacy in Cyberspace. Blockchain Technologies. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-1960-2_2

Häring, I., Fehling-Kaschek, M., Miller, N. et al. A performance-based tabular approach for joint systematic improvement of risk control and resilience applied to telecommunication grid, gas network, and ultrasound localization system. Environ Syst Decis 41, 286–329 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10669-021-09811-5>

Federica Battisti et al. 2020. “Security and Resilience Challenges for the Critical Infrastructures of the Communications Sector” in Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence for Critical Infrastructures Security: A Guide to Integrated Cyber-Physical Protection of Modern Critical Infrastructures. Edited by John Soldatos, James Philpot and Gabriele Giunta. pp. 296–309. Now Publishers. DOI: 10.1561/9781680836875.ch16.

Rodoula Makri et al. 2020. “Modern Innovative Detectors of Physical Threats for Critical Infrastructures” in Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence for Critical Infrastructures Security: A Guide to Integrated CyberPhysical Protection of Modern Critical Infrastructures. Edited by John Soldatos, James Philpot and Gabriele Giunta. pp. 397–414. Now Publishers. DOI: 10.1561/9781680836875.ch22.

Constantin, Ioan & Patachia, Cristian & Patrascu, Carmen & Avadanei, Andrei & Nitescu, Lucian. (2019). Threat classification in current Communication Infrastructures. 1-6. 10.1109/ECAI46879.2019.9042079.

Fehling-Kaschek, M., Miller, N., Haab, G., Faist, K., Stolz, A., Häring, I., Neri, A., Celozzi, G., Sanchez, J., Valera, J., & Makri, R. (2020). Risk and Resilience Assessment and Improvement in the Telecommunication Industry.

In the scope of EU-CIP, a whitepaper on CIP/CIR for the telecommunications sector will be developed. It will focus on the challenges and opportunities of using Dynamic business continuity of telecommunications infrastructures on top of adaptive multi-level cybersecurity. The whitepaper will also present the state of the art of dynamic risk and resilience assessment, as a factor of the business continuity processes in the Telco Sector.

3.3.1.2. Energy

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

The increase of the threat to the perimeter of energy companies and particularly to electrical installations and critical systems is encouraging national and international authorities and regulatory bodies to develop directives and requirements in the field of cyber security. These include the enactment in Europe of the Cyber-ACT (regulation), the NIS (Network Information Security) Directive, which has been converted into the DDADUE Act in French law, and, for some years now, the Military Planning Act (LPM 2014-2019) in France.

Recommendations are part of a defence in depth approach based on identification, prevention, detection, incident response and remediation. It is necessary to assist and support the implementation of better security measures through requirements and procurement. It should enable the organisation to:

- Characterise its current and target cyber security posture.
- Identify gaps in its cyber security risk management programme, using a security analysis logic.
- Understand that existing industry tools, standards and guidelines can support the implementation of recommendations.
- Demonstrate and communicate effectively about its risk management approach and needs identification to internal and external stakeholders.

Identifying critical systems, implementing a protection approach from the design of the installations, being able to detect abnormal functioning in order to react and contain attacks are the essential elements of defence in depth. This should be considered throughout the life cycle of systems that enable the operation of physical and electrotechnical mechanisms (in this case the production and supply of electricity).

These are recent whitepapers considering the level of threat in this domain and the attack landscape (e.g., the Global Electric Cyber Threat Perspective - Dragos 2021⁴⁴, the Schneider Electric Cybersecurity White Paper⁴⁵, the Incident Classification Scale of the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSOE)⁴⁶). The above listed whitepapers will be considered towards developing the EU-CIP whitepaper for challenges and solutions of critical infrastructure protection in the Energy sector.

3.3.1.3. Transport

The transport sector comprises the transport of passengers by aircraft, maritime transport, road or rail and by inland waterway or freight transport services for hire or reward. Creating an environment for safe transport is essential for European citizens. Safety and security are of primary concern for any transport system. Travellers expect transportation to be safe. One of the roles of the European Commission is to respond to these expectations by ensuring that there are satisfactory standards in the whole EU for safety and security in all modes of transport.

⁴⁴ <https://www.dragos.com/resource/electric-utility-cyber-threat-perspective/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.se.com/ww/en/download/document/998-20244304/>,

⁴⁶ https://docstore.entsoe.eu/Documents/SOC%20documents/Incident_Classification_Scale/180411_Incident_Classification_Scale.pdf

Transport security is a sensitive issue that affects all transport users and transport providers. It is a basic right to be able to travel without fear of being a victim of some form of attack. Yet, it is also important that security is not so intrusive as to make travel an unpleasant experience.

Transport security can cover everything from terrorist attacks to prevention of vandalism and graffiti. The Commission's role is to look at measures which, at the EU level, can add value in improving security.

Acts of terrorism are, thankfully, rare events but it must be recognised that transport is a popular target for such actions. As rare as such an event might be, the risk remains, and exposes the vulnerabilities of the entire transport supply chain. Other forms of security threats to transport are more common: crimes committed on the premises of transport operators (like a break-in), stowaways, robbery of valuable cargo in transit, or piracy on the high seas. These have a massive economic cost which can be measured in terms ranging from the cash value of cargo thefts to insurance losses, business interruption and damage to property.

As transport is international in nature it is important to ensure a coordinated EU approach to security standards being developed at ICAO (for aviation security) and IMO (for maritime security). This is complemented by cooperation with third countries on transport security. The Commission consolidates and strengthens security by working together with major international partners, exchanging experiences and best practices.

New technologies can assist in developing smooth high-security systems for the future by reducing the duration and intensity of security checks.

The list below shows a set of recent papers added on behalf of aviation security. EU-CIP will consider these insights and elaborate on them as well as enhance the contents of these papers during the project runtime:

- [Airport-security-white-paper.pdf \(blighter.com\)](#)
- [Aviation White Paper | Department of Infrastructure, Transport, Regional Development, Communications and the Arts](#)
- [IATA-blue-skies-white-paper-2019.pdf](#)
- [Future connectivity for aviation - white paper.pdf](#)
- [White paper - Aircraft Cybersecurity: The Pilot's Perspective \(alpa.org\)](#)
- [A56608 - White Paper on the Aviation Security System.indd \(alpa.org\)](#)
- [Civil aviation and airport security white paper - Duos Technologies \(yumpu.com\)](#)

3.3.1.4. Finance

The infrastructures of the finance sector are of high socio-economic significance, which underlines the importance of their protection. Financial infrastructures are increasingly becoming digital, given the proliferation of the number of digital finance transactions at national, EU (e.g., SEPA (Single Euro Payments Area) transactions) and global levels (e.g., SWIFT (Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunications) transactions). Financial infrastructures have also physical elements (e.g., data centres, ATM, bank branches), yet their security is usually less emphasized than in other industries. During the last couple of years (2018-2021) the FINSEC project studied the physical and

cyber security dimensions of financial infrastructures, along with their interplay and integration. Specifically, FINSEC developed a cyber-physical threat intelligence approach to the security and resilience of critical infrastructures of the finance sector. It also emphasized the importance of information exchange and collaboration across financial institutions towards enhancing their resilience and proactiveness in confronting threats.

FINSEC has also underlined the importance of the cybersecurity part of its solutions, given that the financial sector is one of the most vulnerable and highly attacked industrial sectors. According to recent market studies (e.g., GlobalData 2020), the global cybersecurity revenue for retail banking was \$7.9 billion in 2020 and is estimated to grow at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of more than 8% in the period 2020-2025. This highlights the importance of solutions in areas like risk analysis, risk management, pentesting, security training, and security analytics for cyber assets.

Nowadays the innovation on the security and protection of the critical infrastructures of the finance sector is driven by the regulatory developments as well. The latter include the development of general-purpose regulations (e.g., GDPR, AI Act) as well as sector specific regulations like the 2nd Payment Services Directive (PSD2) and the 4th Anti-Money Laundering Directive (AML), which boost the development of innovative security solutions. From a technological perspective, novel security and resilience solutions are expected to emerge based on recent advances in Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence (AI), financial data spaces, and blockchain technologies. Most importantly, the volatility of the financial environments in the light of occasions like the recent pandemic (COVID19), wars (e.g., Ukrainian war) and financial/banking crises (e.g., SVB bank crises) asks for increased flexibility and resilience.

Motivated by the above-listed development and challenges, EU-CIP intends to provide analysis and foresight about how innovation could strengthen the resilience of financial organizations. Relevant information will be presented in a whitepaper to be provided during the fifth quarter (Q5) of the project. The white paper will illustrate:

- The main drivers of innovative CIP/CIR solutions in the finance sector, including technological, financial and regulatory drivers.
- The main challenges faced by financial organizations at regional, national, EU level with emphasis on their impact on the security and resilience of their critical infrastructures.
- A set of solutions to these challenges, with emphasis on solutions that increase proactivity, flexibility, responsiveness and the overall resilience of financial organizations.

The white paper will update and improve an earlier report developed by INNOV and GFT⁴⁷, which was released in 2021 and (as such) does not capture recent innovation drivers and challenges.

3.3.1.5. Water

Water utilities serve essential societal needs while their services might be utilised in other critical sectors (e.g., in the production of energy) and a halting of operations would have a serious societal and economic impact.

Traditionally, cyber and physical security have been conceived and managed as two separate entities. Water critical infrastructures have always given more attention to physical than cyber security. However, current sophisticated attacks are disrupting both virtual and physical network elements,

⁴⁷ <https://finsecurity.eu/digital-finance-academy-for-security/major-security-challenges/>

giving rise to a wide number of vulnerabilities and complex cyber-physical attacks with potential disastrous consequences.

In addition, today's operating needs have created a technology convergence of physical and cyber infrastructures. Automation has increased due to the need to improve operational efficiencies and workforce shortages. While these changes improve water system operability, they have also created serious vulnerabilities because there has not been a concurrent improvement in the security defence mechanisms [20]. As today's ICS has become IT-centric and highly connected due to the introduction of secondary networks (e.g., the Internet of Things – IoT), the water sector is exposed to the same cybersecurity threats as the IT system, but without appropriate solutions [21].

Furthermore, one of the major challenges the Water sector faces is the lack of cybersecurity situational awareness and the gaps in defines in depth mechanisms. The common believe in many sectors is that a high level of security can be achieved by deploying cutting edge technologies to protect and counter potential risks. However, the truth is that defence in depth can never be achieved if organizations do not clearly understand the relationship of vulnerabilities, threats and the mitigation measures used to protect the operations, personnel, and technologies of an ICS. Defence-in-depth is a holistic approach that considers the interconnections and dependencies among the aforementioned entities while protecting the organization's assets and using their available resources to provide effective layers of monitoring and protection based on the business's exposure to cybersecurity risks [22].

Based on the weaknesses of the sector, the following best practices and recommendations are derived to improve cybersecurity in the water sector and across critical entities [23]:

- Addressing both physical & cyber risk creates a more comprehensive framework for sectors such as the water & wastewater sector.
- The scope of information sharing between different critical entities in Europe should be further expanded to effectively encourage cooperation and communication.
- Need to increase the efforts on raising awareness in cybersecurity across the various EU critical sectors, including the water sector.
- Utilise the benefit of adopting risk management approaches and solutions developed in recent EU funded research projects by H2020 (e.g., from INFRA, Critical Infrastructure Protection - CIP calls) and other programmes to overcome some of the implementation challenges of the proposed Critical Entities Resilience (CER) Directive and the NIS-2.
- Promote training activities for water operators at different decision level for an effective and adequate response; training should be based on core courses, augmented by a training programme involving discussion and operational exercises based on realistic and plausible scenarios.

In the terms of policy implications, the recommendations are:

The recommendations are (see also [23]):

- Authorities should strive for collaborative tools to share information and to create collective situational awareness of cyber threats.
- Create competence development programmes on cyber security in the water sector.
- Support initiatives, as the EU Water ISAC, as secure environment for information and best practice sharing, as well as for training initiatives and activities.

Progress regarding the uptake of digital solutions by utilities has been hindered by a perceived risk of lack of security. This is a risk that can be minimised through the use of appropriate technologies and

tools to secure the Digital Water Systems; although such security tools that integrate cyber-physical risk approaches exist and have been tested (as in STOP-IT), they have not yet been broadly accepted by the water sector. The implementation of those solutions should be supported.

3.3.1.6. Maritime

European Union ports are currently facing cyber-physical threats which can potentially cause hundreds of thousands of casualties and have an impact of tens of billion euros in the EU economy. Special attention will be paid to the integration into SAURON platform of the communities and specific infrastructures and assets in the vicinity of the ports. SAURON, led by a critical infrastructure operator, will achieve its objectives through 4 specific, exploitable results which will be validated in real conditions with the direct involvement of 4 EU ports.

Nowadays coordinated and increasingly complex terrorist attacks are shocking the world. Due to the progressive reliance of the industrial sector and many CI, in particular EU ports on ICT systems, the impact of a coordinated physical attack, a deliberate disruption of critical automation (cyber) systems or even a combined scenario including both kind of attacks, could have disastrous consequences for the European Member States' regions and social wellbeing in general.

Emergency Population Warning System (EPWS), or national authorities can contact members of the public and masse to warn them of an impending emergency. These warnings may be necessary for a number of reasons, including:

- Weather emergencies such as floods, hurricanes, etc.
- Geological disasters such as earthquakes, landslides, volcanic eruptions, or tsunamis.
- Industrial disasters such as the release of toxic gas or chemical contamination.
- Radiological disasters such as a nuclear plant disaster.
- Medical emergencies such as an outbreak of a fast-moving infectious disease.
- Warfare or acts of terrorism.

The EU-CIP whitepaper for the maritime sector will elaborate on modern CIP challenges for maritime infrastructures (e.g., coordinated physical attacks) and will highlight possible solutions building on existing outcomes (e.g., SAURON).

3.3.1.7. Industry

The industry sector refers to the part of the economy concerned with the production of goods and services through industrial processes. It includes a wide range of activities, from manufacturing to mining, construction, and utilities. The industry sector is an essential component of modern economies, providing employment opportunities, generating income, and contributing to economic growth. The industrial sector is experiencing a profound transformation, in which the convergence between systems, data and processes used throughout the lifecycle of the product is crucial, from design in the office to production in the factory, from supply chain in the warehouse to use of the finished product by the end customer. Interconnected technologies are the necessary anchors. The industry sector plays a vital role in the global economy, contributing significantly to employment, trade, and technological innovation. It has undergone significant changes in recent decades due to

advances in technology, globalization, and changing consumer preferences. As a result, companies in the industry sector have had to adapt to remain competitive and meet the changing demands of consumers and businesses. Some trends emerging in the current context are:

- **Automation:** With advances in technology, many industries are increasingly automating their production processes to improve efficiency and reduce costs. This has led to the development of technologies such as robotics and artificial intelligence, which are transforming the way goods and services are produced.
- **Sustainable production:** Many companies in the industry sector are adopting more sustainable practices in their production processes, such as using renewable energy sources, reducing waste and emissions, and recycling materials.
- **Globalization:** The industry sector is increasingly globalized, with companies operating in multiple countries and relying on global supply chains to produce goods and services. This has created new opportunities for growth and innovation but also poses challenges such as increased competition and supply chain disruptions.
- **Digitalization:** The industry sector is also undergoing digital transformation, with companies using digital technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and data analytics to improve efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance customer experiences.
- **Shift to services:** While traditional manufacturing industries are still significant, there has been a shift towards service-oriented industries, such as healthcare, finance, and information technology. These industries often rely on technology and innovation to provide services, rather than physical goods.
- **Skilled labour shortage:** Many companies in the industry sector are facing a shortage of skilled labour, particularly in areas such as engineering, technology, and operations. This has led to increased investment in training and education programs to develop the skills needed to meet industry demands.

Throughout the globe, the traditional industry sector is in the midst of a massive Digital Transformation, growing each day by evolving newer technology solutions. The interaction between the virtual and real worlds is opening up new ways for companies to integrate their customers' needs and preferences into their product development and production processes. Organizations that pay more attention to the possibilities offered by new technologies, on the wave of Industry 4.0 dynamics, are already changing their capabilities and designing the future playing field for themselves and their competitors [24].

4. Conclusions and Outlook for Future Work

This report marks the beginning of a series of value-added publications under the EU-CIP-ANALYSIS pillar of the EU-CIP Coordination and Support Action (CSA). In this edition, we have mapped the European landscape for Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR), highlighting key EU-funded initiatives, the latest technological and policy developments, and relevant standards. We have also initiated a dialogue with stakeholders across the CIP/CIR ecosystem, gathering early insights into existing gaps and emerging needs.

Our initial findings underscore the importance of continued collaboration and evidence-based innovation. By engaging with experts and stakeholders, we are laying the groundwork for a more resilient and secure critical infrastructure environment in Europe.

Looking ahead, future reports will build on this foundation by providing:

- **A deeper analysis of the European CIP/CIR market**, including trends, challenges, and opportunities beyond research initiatives.
- **A comprehensive assessment of capability gaps and needs**, with actionable recommendations for addressing them.
- **Detailed roadmaps and planning strategies** to guide research, innovation, and policy development, complete with timelines and implementation guidelines.
- **Sector-specific whitepapers and value-added reports** that deliver targeted insights and practical guidance for industry, policymakers, and other stakeholders.

The ultimate goal of the EU-CIP-ANALYSIS pillar is to deliver forward-looking analysis and practical tools that empower the CIP/CIR community. By providing regular, high-value insights, we aim to support the planning, design, and implementation of future initiatives—ensuring that Europe’s critical infrastructures remain robust, secure, and adaptable to evolving challenges.

We invite all stakeholders to stay engaged as we continue to share new findings, actionable intelligence, and strategic guidance in the coming months.

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6. Annex I: Information Collection Forms

1. First Name *

2. Last Name *

3. Organisation *

4. e-mail *

5. Specify the SECTOR you are referring to *

6. Which are the main capability needs in Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR) in your sector?

7. Which are the main gaps of existing solutions in Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR) in your sector?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

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8. Which are the state of the art technologies and tools that can help closing the gaps in Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR) in your sector?

- Adaptive threat hunting
- Anomaly Detection
- Biometric Authentication
- Blockchain/DLT Technology
- Closed Circuit Television Systems
- Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence
- Cybersecurity Tools
- Data Loss Prevention Technology
- Digital twins
- Disinformation Management
- End-Point Protection
- Image Analysis
- Impact assessment tools
- Machine Learning – Pattern Detection
- Modelling of cascading effects and interdependencies between CIs
- Pentesting
- Security Information and Event Management
- Security Risk Assessment
- Social Media Analysis
- Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
- Visual Scene Analysis
- Sandboxes
- Social Graph Analysis
- Surveillance Systems
- Malware Detection
- Ransomware
- 5G Communications – Internet of Things
-

9. Describe in 2-3 lines at most, the novel applications of some of the above technologies and innovations in your sector?

10. In which of the following CIP/CIR phases do you phase the most challenges in your sector?

- Prediction & Anticipation
- Prevention
- Detection
- Response
- Recovery
- Combination or Integration of two or more (please specify)
-

11. Do you participate or have you participated in any H2020/HEU project in CIP/CIR or related security topics?

- ANASTACIA
- CyberSANE
- CyberSEAS
- DEFENDER
- EnergyShield
- ENSURESEC
- EU-HYBNET
- FeatureCloud
- FINSEC
- IMPETUS
- InfraStress
- PHOENIX
- PRAETORIAN
- PRECINCT
- RESISTO
- SAFECARE
- SAFETY4RAILS
- SATIE
- SealedGRID
- SecureGas
- SmartResilience
- SOTER
- SPHINX
- STOP-IT
- 7SHIELD
- Digital Water city
-

12. For each one of the projects where you participated, please name the three most important technical/technological CIP/CIR outcomes (e.g., available and permitted by the confidentiality level), please provide a link to some relevant site, paper or deliverable.

13. For each one of the projects where you participated, please name the three most important non-technological CIP/CIR outcomes (e.g., legal, ethical, regulatory, standardization). If possible (e.g., available and permitted by the confidentiality level), please provide a link to some relevant site, paper or deliverable.

14. Please name the five most important CIP/CIR trends in your sector according to your opinion:

- Adaptive Threat Hunting
- Autonomous adaptive security
- Automation using Artificial Intelligence
- Collaborative Threat Intelligence
- Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence Integration
- Federated Attack Libraries
- Federated Security Knowledge Bases
- Fighting misinformation
- Predictive Security
- Threat anticipation
-

15. Please name / refer to some important lessons learnt and/or best practices from your projects and experience. Provide any relevant pointer (if possible)

16. What are the main standards influencing CIP/CIR in your sector?

- ISO/TC 292 Security and Resilience : WG2 & WG5
- ISO 28000 series
- ISO 28000:2022 S
- ISO 28002:2011
- ISO 22000 series: ISO 22301:2019 / ISO 22300:2021 / ISO/TR 22845:2020 / ISO 22324:2022/ISO 22322:2022 /ISO 22325:2016/ISO 22316:2017 /ISO 22313:2020 /ISO 22396:2020 /ISO 22392:2020 /ISO 22384:2020 /ISO/TS 22331:2018 /ISO/TS 22375:2018 /ISO/TS 22318:2021 /ISO/TS22317:2021/ISO/TS 22332:2021/ ISO 22320:2018/ ISO 22326:2018 / ISO/TS 22375:2018
- Under development: ISO/AWI 8928/ ISO 22385 /ISO 22361 /ISO/AWI 22300 Security and resilience /ISO/FDIS 22393 / ISO/DIS 22376 /ISO/WD 22373/ ISO/CD 22336 /
- ISO/TC 262 Risk management
- Under development: ISO/CD TS 31050, ISO/TC 267/WG 1, ISO/AWI TR41019
- ISO / IEC: ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27 : Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection. Scope: The development of standards for the protection of information and ICT. This includes generic methods, techniques and guidelines to address both security and privacy aspects
- ISO 27000 family of standards: ISO/IEC 27005 :2022 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Guidance on managing information security risks; ISO/IEC 27032:2012/ISO/IEC 27400:2022 /ISO/IEC 27036-2:2022 /ISO/IEC TR 5895:2022; ISO/IEC 27036-1:2021 / ISO/IEC 27001:2022/ ISO/IEC 27005:2022 /ISO/IEC 27002:2022 ; /ISO/IEC 27002:2022/ ISO/IEC 18045:2022/ISO/IEC 27559:2022 /ISO/IEC 27557:2022; / ISO/IEC 27556:2022/ ISO/IEC 27013:2021 / ISO/IEC 27551:2021/ISO/IEC 27555:2021; / ISO/IEC 27014:2020 / ISO/IEC 27009:2020
- Under development: ISO/IEC DIS 27402 / ISO/IEC DIS 24392/ ISO/IEC DIS 27032 / ISO/IEC AWI 27090 /; ISO/IEC DIS 27071/ ISO/IEC FDIS 27036-3 / ISO/IEC CD TR 6114 / ISO/IEC CD TR 6114 /ISO/IEC CD 27403.2/ ISO/IEC AWI 27028/ ISO/IEC CD TS 9569 / ISO/IEC CD TR 5891
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 30
- Under development: ISO/IEC CD 9837-1; ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 39 Sustainability, IT and data centres
- Under development: ISO/IEC WD TS 22237-31
- ISA/IEC
- IEC 62443 Industrial communication networks - Network and system security: IEC 62443-2-1; IEC 62443-2-2; IEC 62443-2-4; IEC 62443-3-3; IEC 62443-4-1; IEC 62443-4-2
- IEC 61850: ISO/PWI 6367
- CEN: CEN/CLC/WS 018 ;; CWA 17819:2021
- Other standards-related publications: NIST 800.53; NERC CIP Exec Order 14028; EU Cybersecurity Act (EU CSA); Cyber Resilience Act (EU CRA); EU's Radio Equipment Directive 2014/53/EU (EU RED); EU NIS 2
-

17. What are the main gaps and needs for training and education for security/safety teams in your sector?

18. Have you/your organisation been involved in – or are planning to initiate - efforts to commercialise CIP/CIR solutions through product development, spinout, start-up, licensing or other means?

- Yes
- No
- If Yes, specify in the box below:
-

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7. Annex II: Internal Stakeholders Feedback Form

Name/Surname (Optional for External Stakeholders):

Organization (Optional for External Stakeholders):

Sector:

E-mail (Optional for External Stakeholders):

1. Which are the main capability needs in Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR) in your sector?

2. Which are the main gaps of existing solutions in Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR) in your sector?

3. Which are the state of the art technologies and tools that can help closing the gaps in Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR) in your sector?

- a) Adaptive threat hunting
- b) Anomaly Detection
- c) Biometric Authentication
- d) Blockchain/DLT Technology
- e) Closed Circuit Television Systems
- f) Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence
- g) Cybersecurity Tools
- h) Data Loss Prevention Technology
- i) Digital twins
- j) Disinformation Management
- k) End-Point Protection
- l) Image Analysis
- m) Impact assessment tools
- n) Machine Learning – Pattern Detection
- o) Modelling of cascading effects and interdependencies between CIs
- p) Pentesting
- q) Security Information and Event Management
- r) Security Risk Assessment
- s) Social Media Analysis
- t) Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
- u) Visual Scene Analysis
- v) Sandboxes

- w) Social Graph Analysis
- x) Surveillance Systems
- y) Malware Detection
- z) Ransomware
- aa) 5G Communications – Internet of Things
- bb) Other – please specify: _____

4. Describe in 2-3 lines at most, the novel applications of some of the above technologies and innovations in your sector?

5. In which of the following CIP/CIR phases do you phase the most challenges in your sector?

- a. Prediction & Anticipation
- b. Prevention
- c. Detection
- d. Response
- e. Recovery
- f. Combination or Integration of two or more – please specify: _____
- g. Other – please specify: _ _____

6. Do you participate or have you participated in any H2020/HEU project in CIP/CIR or related security topics?

- a) ANASTACIA
- b) CyberSANE
- c) CyberSEAS
- d) DEFENDER
- e) EnergyShield
- f) ENSURESEC
- g) EU-HYBNET
- h) FeatureCloud
- i) FINSEC
- j) IMPETUS
- k) InfraStress
- l) PHOENIX
- m) PRAETORIAN
- n) PRECINCT
- o) RESISTO
- p) SAFECARE
- q) SAFETY4RAILS
- r) SATIE
- s) SealedGRID
- t) SecureGas

- u) SmartResilience
- v) SOTER
- w) SPHINX
- x) STOP-IT
- y) 7SHIELD
- z) Digital-Water.city.....
- aa) Other – please specify: _____

7. For each one of the projects where you participated, please name the three most important technical/technological CIP/CIR outcomes. If possible (e.g., available and permitted by the confidentiality level), please provide a link to some relevant site, paper or deliverable.

8. For each one of the projects where you participated, please name the three most important non-technological CIP/CIR outcomes (e.g., legal, ethical, regulatory, standardization). If possible (e.g., available and permitted by the confidentiality level), please provide a link to some relevant site, paper or deliverable.

9. Please name the five most important CIP/CIR trends in your sector according to your opinion:

- a) Adaptive Threat Hunting
- b) Autonomous adaptive security
- c) Automation using Artificial Intelligence
- d) Collaborative Threat Intelligence
- e) Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence Integration
- f) Federated Attack Libraries
- g) Federated Security Knowledge Bases
- h) Fighting misinformation
- i) Predictive Security
- j) Threat anticipation
- k) Other – please specify: _____

10. Please name / refer to some important lessons learnt and/or best practices from your projects and experience. Provide any relevant pointer (if possible)

- a) Lesson 1:
- b) Lesson 2:
- c) Best Practice 1:
- d) Best Practice 2:

11. What are the main standards influencing CIP/CIR in your sector?

ISO/TC 292 Security and Resilience : WG2 & WG5

ISO 28000 series

ISO 28000:2022 S

ISO 28002:2011

ISO 22000 series

- ISO 22301:2019 / ISO 22300:2021 / ISO/TR 22845:2020 / ISO 22324:2022/ISO 22322:2022 /ISO 22325:2016/ISO 22316:2017 /ISO 22313:2020 /ISO 22396:2020 /ISO 22392:2020 /ISO 22384:2020 /ISO/TS 22331:2018 /ISO/TS 22375:2018 /ISO/TS 22318:2021 /ISO/TS22317:2021/ISO/TS 22332:2021/ ISO 22320:2018/ ISO 22326:2018 / ISO/TS 22375:2018

Under development

- ISO/AWI 8928/ ISO 22385 /ISO 22361 /ISO/AWI 22300 Security and resilience /ISO/FDIS 22393 / ISO/DIS 22376 /ISO/WD 22373/ ISO/CD 22336 /

ISO/TC 262 Risk management

Under development

- ISO/CD TS 31050
- ISO/TC 267/WG 1
- ISO/AWI TR41019

ISO / IEC

- ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27 : Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection
- Scope : The development of standards for the protection of information and ICT. This includes generic methods, techniques and guidelines to address both security and privacy aspects

ISO 27000 family of standards

- ISO/IEC 27005 :2022 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection – Guidance on managing information security risks
- ISO/IEC 27032:2012/ISO/IEC 27400:2022 /ISO/IEC 27036-2:2022 /ISO/IEC TR 5895:2022
- ISO/IEC 27036-1:2021 / ISO/IEC 27001:2022/ ISO/IEC 27005:2022 /ISO/IEC 27002:2022 /
- ISO/IEC 27002:2022/ ISO/IEC 18045:2022/ISO/IEC 27559:2022 /ISO/IEC 27557:2022
- / ISO/IEC 27556:2022/ ISO/IEC 27013:2021 / ISO/IEC 27551:2021/ISO/IEC 27555:2021
- / ISO/IEC 27014:2020 / ISO/IEC 27009:2020

Under development

- ISO/IEC DIS 27402 / ISO/IEC DIS 24392/ ISO/IEC DIS 27032 / ISO/IEC AWI 27090 /
- ISO/IEC DIS 27071/ ISO/IEC FDIS 27036-3 / ISO/IEC CD TR 6114 / ISO/IEC CD TR 6114 /
- ISO/IEC CD 27403.2/ ISO/IEC AWI 27028/ ISO/IEC CD TS 9569 / ISO/IEC CD TR 5891

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 30

Under development

- ISO/IEC CD 9837-1
 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 39 Sustainability, IT and data centres
- Under development
- ISO/IEC WD TS 22237-31

ISA/IEC

IEC 62443 Industrial communication networks - Network and system security

- IEC 62443-2-1
- IEC 62443-2-2
- IEC 62443-2-4
- IEC 62443-3-3
- IEC 62443-4-1
- IEC 62443-4-2

IEC 61850

- ISO/PWI 6367

CEN

- CEN/CLC/WS 018 :
- CWA 17819:2021

Other standards-related publications

- NIST 800.53
- NERC CIP Exec Order 14028
- EU Cybersecurity Act (EU CSA)
- Cyber Resilience Act (EU CRA)
- EU's Radio Equipment Directive 2014/53/EU (EU RED)
- EU NIS 2

Other (please specify): _____

12. What are the main gaps and needs for training and education for security/safety teams in your sector?

13. Have you/your organisation been involved in – or are planning to initiate - efforts to commercialise CIP/CIR solutions through product development, spinout, start-up, licensing or other means?

YES/NO
(i) If yes, please give details where possible.

8. Annex III: Description of EU Funded CIP Projects

EU Funded Projects on Critical Infrastructure Protection

7SHIELD: Keeping space data safe from physical and cyber threats: The EU-funded 7SHIELD project developed a holistic framework enabling the deployment of innovative services for the cyber–physical protection of ground segments. This includes e-fences, passive radars and laser technologies. The project made use of advanced technologies for data integration, processing, analytics and visualisation as well as data security and cyberthreat protection to assess the prevention, detection and mitigation of threats, both physical and cyber.

ANASTACIA: The main objective of the ANASTACIA project is to address cyber-security concerns by researching, developing and demonstrating a holistic solution enabling trust and security by-design for Cyber Physical Systems (CPS) based on IoT and Cloud architectures.

ATLANTIS: The main aim of the ATLANTIS project is to improve the resilience and the protection capabilities of interconnected critical infrastructure exposed to evolving risks through novel, flexible and customisable security measures and tools. It addresses resilience at the systemic level against major natural hazards and complex attacks that could potentially disrupt vital functions of the society.

CONCORDIA: A cybersecurity competence network boosting the EU’s digital sovereignty: The EU-funded CONCORDIA, a multi-disciplinary research and innovation project, has set out to address this current fragmentation and further enhance the EU's digital sovereignty. The project interconnected all of Europe’s cybersecurity capabilities into a network of expertise to help build a secure, trusted, resilient and competitive ecosystem. Moreover, it developed the EU Cybersecurity Research and Innovation Roadmap.

CyberSANE CyberSANE is designing and implementing an advanced, configurable and adaptable, Security and Privacy Incident Handling Systems, towards security incident detection and handling, composed of five independent but collaborative components: LiveNet (Live Security Monitoring and Analysis), DarkNet (Deep and Dark Web Mining and Intelligence), HybridNet (Data Fusion, Risk Evaluation and Event Management), ShareNet (Intelligence and Information Sharing and Dissemination), and PrivacyNet (Privacy & Data Protection Orchestrator).

CyberSEAS: The CyberSEAS project aims to improve the overall resilience of energy supply chains, protecting them from disruptions that exploit the enhanced interactions, the extended involvement models of stakeholders and consumers as channels for complex cyber-attacks, the presence of legacy systems and the increasing connectivity of energy infrastructures, data stores and services retailers.

DEFENDER: The main objectives of the DEFENDER project are to (i) model CEIs (Critical Energy infrastructures) as distributed Cyber-Physical Systems for managing the potential reciprocal effects of cyber and physical threats (ii) deploy a novel security governance model, which leverages on lifecycle assessment for cost-effective security management over the time, and (iii) bring people at centre stage by empowering them as

virtual sensors for threat detection, as first level emergency responders to attacks, or by considering workforce as potential threats.

Digital-Water.City: Digital solutions for water management: The EU-funded Digital-Water.City project aimed to promote integrated water management in urban and peri-urban areas of five big EU cities with the support of data and smart digital solutions. It has developed digital solutions to face gaps related to ICT governance, semantic interoperability and cybersecurity topics.

DYNABIC: The main aim of the DYNABIC project is to increase the resilience and business continuity capabilities of European critical services in the face of advanced cyber-physical threats by delivering new socio-technical methods, models and tools to support resilience through holistic business continuity risk management and control in operation, and dynamic adaptation of responses at system, human and organization planes.

EnergyShield: EnergyShield captures the needs of Electrical Power and Energy System (EPES) operators and combines the latest technologies for vulnerability assessment, supervision and protection to draft a defensive toolkit for shielding the power grid from cyberattacks.

ENSURESEC: The ENSURESEC project will address cyber and physical threats for e-commerce in the digital single market to improve the EU's vision of a reliable and trusted digital single market. It will develop innovations applicable to any critical infrastructure that relies on and is monitored by networked software systems. The project will address threats ranging from malicious modification of web e-commerce applications to delivery issues or fraud committed by insiders or customers.

EU-HYBNET: EU-HYBNET focuses specifically on the preparation for and defending against hybrid threats, as well as on the development and building of a European network for the sector, bring together practitioners and stakeholders to identify the most urgent needs for countering hybrid threats, and undertake in-depth analysis of the gaps and needs and test the most promising innovations (technical and social).

FeatureCloud: The FeatureCloud project proposes a transformative security-by-design concept aiming to reduce the possibility of cybercrime and allow safe cross-border collaborative data mining efforts. It will integrate federated machine learning with blockchain technology to safely apply next-generation AI technology in medical innovations.

FINSEC: The EU-funded FINSEC project introduces a novel standards-based reference architecture (RA) for integrated (cyber & physical) security, which will enable timely preparation against attacks, while at the same time facilitating stakeholders' collaboration for risk assessment/mitigation in the financial supply chain, as a means of confronting complex threats and their cascading effects. FINSEC will provide a mature implementation of the RA, based on the enhancement and integration of novel solutions of the partners (e.g., Anomaly Detection, AI CCTV Analytics, Risk Assessment Engines, Collaborative Risk Analysis & Management, Compliance), which will be bundled in a toolbox.

IMPETUS: A system for increased urban security: The EU-funded IMPETUS project will develop an instrument that covers the entire physical and cybersecurity value chain, increasing city resilience to security events in public areas. It will apply IoT, AI and Big

Data technologies, ensure smart city capabilities in protecting personal data and establish a multi-tenant solution entirely coordinated with the operational needs of a wide range of city stakeholders.

InfraStress: Managing industrial-level threats with an open-testbed system: InfraStress will build on preceding research towards a Technology Readiness Level 7 solution that includes threat detection, situational awareness, input from end-users and evaluation activities, presented in user-friendly services. It also hopes to help cultivate a culture of participation among all involved stakeholders, from the private and public sector to civil society and citizens.

PANOPTIS: The PANOPTIS project aims at increasing the resilience of the road infrastructures and ensuring reliable network availability under unfavourable conditions, such as extreme weather, landslides, and earthquakes. The main target is to combine downscaled climate change scenarios (applied to road infrastructures) with simulation tools (structural/geotechnical) and actual data (from existing and novel sensors), so as to provide the operators with an integrated tool.

PHOENIX: PHOENIX aims to offer a cyber-shield armour to European EPES infrastructure enabling cooperative detection of large scale, cyber-human security and privacy incidents and attacks, guarantee the continuity of operations and minimize cascading effects in the infrastructure itself, the environment, the citizens and the end-users at reasonable cost.

PRAETORIAN: Protection of critical infrastructures from advanced combined cyber and physical threats: The EU-funded PRAETORIAN project delivers a multidimensional installation-specific toolset comprising a physical situation awareness system, a cyber situation awareness system, a hybrid situation awareness system (including digital twins), and a coordinated response system including a decision support system. The project will deal with human-made cyber- and physical attacks or natural disasters and demonstrate its results in two international airports, two ports, three hospitals and two power plants. It will also consider potential cascading effects.

PRECINCT: Cyber-physical security management for critical infrastructures (CI): The EU-funded PRECINCT project will connect private and public CI stakeholders in a geographical area to a cyber-physical security management method that will produce a protected territory for citizens and CIs. The project will deliver a framework specification for systematic CI security and resilience management, a cross-facility collaborative management infrastructure enabling stakeholder communities to create AI-based PRECINCT ecosystems and increased resilience support services, a vulnerability assessment tool using serious games, PRECINCT's Digital Twins, and PRECINCT Ecosystems in four large-scale living labs and transferability validation demonstrators.

RESISTO: Based on an Integrated Risk and Resilience analysis management and improvement process availing all resilience cycle phases (prepare, prevent, detect, absorb, etc.) and technical resilience capabilities (sense, model, infer, act, adopt), the RESISTO project implements an innovative Decision Support System to protect communication infrastructures from combined cyber-physical threats exploiting the Software Defined Security model on a suite of state of the art cyber/physical security components (Blockchain, Machine Learning, IoT security, Airborne threat detection, holistic audio-

video analytics) and services (Responsible Disclosure Framework) for detection and reaction in presence of attacks or natural disasters.

SAFECARE: The aim of this SAFECARE project is to provide solutions that will improve physical and cyber security in a seamless and cost-effective way, to promote new technologies and novel approaches to enhance threat prevention, threat detection, incident response and mitigation of impacts, and to participate in increasing the compliance between security tools and European regulations about ethics and privacy for health services.

SAFETY4RAILS: Keeping railways safe from cyberattacks: The EU-funded SAFETY4RAILS project will develop methods to increase the safety and recovery of track-based intercity railway and intracity metro transportation by focussing on physical-only and cyber-only attacks, as well as combined cyber-physical attacks. It will analyse the cyber-physical resilience of metro and railway systems and deliver mitigation strategies for an efficient response to ensure reliable transportation also in situations with a high volume of passengers.

SATIE: New toolkit to boost airport security: The EU-funded SATIE project will create new 'Security Operation Centre' philosophies for inclusion in a comprehensive airport security policy. This will include a holistic approach on threat prevention, detection, response and mitigation in airports, while ensuring the protection of critical systems, sensitive data and passengers. To do this, SATIE will develop an interoperable toolkit that will help improve cyber-physical correlations, forensic investigations and dynamic impact assessment at airports.

SAURON: The project attempts to ensure an adequate level of both physical and cyber protection for the EU ports and limiting, as far as possible, the detrimental effects for the society and citizens of a combined attack (physical & cyber) to an EU port. Taking into account this fact and this real threat on EU ports as one of the main CI in Europe, the SAURON project proposes a holistic situation awareness concept as an integrated, scalable and yet installation-specific solution for protecting EU ports and its surroundings.

SealedGRID: SealedGRID aims at bringing together experts from industry and academia from cross-sectorial research areas having complementary background with the long-term goal to design, analyse, and implement a scalable, highly trusted and interoperable smart grid security platform which will combine, for the very first time, technologies like Blockchain, Distributed Hash Tables, Trusted Execution Environments, and OpenID Connect.

SecureGas: An integrated action plan to protect and fortify Europe's gas network: The EU-funded SecureGas project proposes a resilience-based management of gas assets and infrastructures, built on a case-by-case integration, adaptation and customisation of advance components and technical solutions. The project aims to secure existing and forthcoming installations and make them resilient to both physical and cyberthreats, ultimately ensuring the safety and security of Europe's energy supply.

SmartResilience: The SmartResilience project identifies existing indicators suitable for assessing resilience of smart critical infrastructures (SCIs), identifies new "smart" resilience indicators (RIs) – including those from Big Data, develops a new advanced resilience assessment methodology (TRL4) based on smart RIs ("resilience indicators

cube”, including the resilience matrix), develops the interactive “SCI Dashboard” tool, and applies the methodology/tools in 8 case studies, integrated under one virtual, smart-city-like, European case study.

SOTER: Tools to protect against cyber-attacks: SOTER creates tools to tackle future cyberattacks and vulnerabilities to improve the interconnections between different service providers and users and help identify the level of cybersecurity that exists and to reinforce trust in their information and communications technology products, services and processes.

SPHINX: New toolkit to secure all medical data: The EU-funded SPHINX project ensures the cyber protection of the health IT ecosystem for patient data privacy and integrity by developing a Universal Cyber Security Toolkit. Based on an automated zero-touch device and service verification, the toolkit will be ready to be integrated with existing health infrastructures.

STOP-IT: The EU-funded STOP-IT project assembled a team of major Water Utilities, industrial technology developers, high tech SMEs and top EU R&D providers. It has organized communities of practice for water systems protection to identify current and future risk landscapes and to co-develop an all-hazards risk management framework for the physical and cyber protection of water critical infrastructures. Prevention, Detection, Response and Mitigation of relevant risks at strategic, tactical and operational levels of planning have been taken into account to generate modular solutions (technologies, tools and guidelines) and an integrated software platform.

SUNRISE: The SUNRISE project aims to ensure greater availability, reliability, and continuity of critical infrastructures in Europe including transport, energy, water, and healthcare to tackle future pandemics by facilitating collaboration, cooperation, and unity among public and private critical infrastructure operators and competent authorities across different critical sectors and across entire Europe, discouraging them to work in isolation.

9. Annex IV: ISO Standards for Risk Management in CIP/CIR

Standard	Title
ISO 18788:2015	Management system for private security operations – Requirements with guidance for use
ISO 22300:2021	Security and resilience – Vocabulary
ISO/AWI 22300	Security and resilience – Vocabulary
ISO 22301:2019	Security and resilience – Business continuity management systems – Requirements
ISO 22311:2012	Societal security – Video-surveillance – Export interoperability
ISO 22313:2020	Security and resilience – Business continuity management systems – Guidance on the use of ISO 22301
ISO 22315:2014	Societal security – Mass evacuation – Guidelines for planning
ISO 22316:2017	Security and resilience – Organizational resilience – Principles and attributes
ISO/AWI 22316	Security and resilience – Organizational resilience – Principles and attributes
ISO/TS 22317:2021	Security and resilience – Business continuity management systems – Guidelines for business impact analysis
ISO/TS 22318:2021	Security and resilience – Business continuity management systems – Guidelines for supply chain continuity management
ISO 22319:2017	Security and resilience – Community resilience – Guidelines for planning the involvement of spontaneous volunteers
ISO 22320:2018	Security and resilience – Emergency management – Guidelines for incident management
ISO 22322:2022	Security and resilience – Emergency management – Guidelines for public warning
ISO 22324:2022	Security and resilience – Emergency management – Guidelines for colour-coded alert
ISO 22325:2016	Security and resilience – Emergency management – Guidelines for capability assessment
ISO 22326:2018	Security and resilience – Emergency management – Guidelines for monitoring facilities with identified hazards
ISO 22327:2018	Security and resilience – Emergency management – Guidelines for implementation of a community-based landslide early warning system
ISO 22328-1:2020	Security and resilience – Emergency management – Part 1: General guidelines for the implementation of a community-based disaster early warning system
ISO/DIS 22328-2	Security and resilience – Emergency management – Part 2: Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based early warning system for landslides
ISO 22328-3:2023	Security and resilience – Emergency management – Part 3: Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based early warning system for tsunamis
ISO 22329:2021	Security and resilience – Emergency management – Guidelines for the use of social media in emergencies

ISO/TS 22330:2018	Security and resilience – Business continuity management systems – Guidelines for people aspects of business continuity
ISO/TS 22331:2018	Security and resilience – Business continuity management systems – Guidelines for business continuity strategy
ISO/TS 22332:2021	Security and resilience – Business continuity management systems – Guidelines for developing business continuity plans and procedures
ISO/CD 22336	Security and resilience – Organizational resilience – Guidelines for resilience policy and strategy
ISO/CD 22340	Security and resilience – Protective security – Guidelines for an enterprise protective security architecture and framework
ISO 22341:2021	Security and resilience – Protective security – Guidelines for crime prevention through environmental design
ISO 22342	Security and resilience – Protective security – Guidelines for the development of a security plan for an organization
ISO/FDIS 22343-1	Security and resilience – Vehicle security barriers – Part 1: Performance requirement, vehicle impact test method and performance rating
ISO/FDIS 22343-2	Security and resilience – Vehicle security barriers – Part 2: Application
ISO/CD 22344	Security and resilience – Protective security – Guidelines for crime prevention through environmental design for residential facilities
ISO/TR 22351:2015	Societal security – Emergency management – Message structure for exchange of information
ISO/CD 22359	Security and resilience – Hardened protective shelters – Guidelines
ISO/WD TS 22360.2	Security and resilience – Crisis management – Concept, principles and framework
ISO 22361:2022	Security and resilience – Crisis management – Guidelines
ISO/AWI 22366	Security and resilience – Energy resilience – Framework and principles
ISO/TR 22370:2020	Security and resilience – Urban resilience – Framework and principles
ISO/WD 22372	Security and resilience – Resilient Infrastructure – Guidelines
ISO/WD 22373	Security and resilience – Authenticity, integrity and trust for products and documents – Framework for establishing trustworthy supply chains
ISO/TS 22375:2018	Security and resilience – Guidelines for complexity assessment process
ISO/FDIS 22376	Security and resilience – Authenticity, integrity and trust for products and documents – Specification and usage of Visible Digital Seal (VDS) data format for authentication, verification and acquisition of data carried by a document or object
ISO 22378:2022	Security and resilience – Authenticity, integrity and trust for products and documents – Guidelines for interoperable object

	identification and related authentication systems to deter counterfeiting and illicit trade
ISO 22379:2022	Security and resilience – Guidelines for hosting and organizing citywide or regional events
ISO 22380:2018	Security and resilience – Authenticity, integrity and trust for products and documents – General principles for product fraud risk and countermeasures
ISO 22381:2018	Security and resilience – Authenticity, integrity and trust for products and documents – Guidelines for establishing interoperability among object identification systems to deter counterfeiting and illicit trade
ISO 22382:2018	Security and resilience – Authenticity, integrity and trust for products and documents – Guidelines for the content, security, issuance and examination of excise tax stamps
ISO 22383:2020	Security and resilience – Authenticity, integrity and trust for products and documents – Guidelines for the selection and performance evaluation of authentication solutions for material goods
ISO 22384:2020	Security and resilience – Authenticity, integrity and trust for products and documents – Guidelines to establish and monitor a protection plan and its implementation
ISO 22385:2023	Security and resilience – Authenticity, integrity and trust for products and documents – Guidelines to establish a framework for trust and interoperability
ISO/CD TS 22386	Security and resilience – Authenticity, integrity and trust for products and documents – Guidelines for brand protection and enforcement procedures
ISO 22387:2022	Security and resilience – Authenticity, integrity and trust for products and documents – Validation procedures for the application of artefact metrics
ISO/DIS 22388	Security and resilience – Authenticity, integrity and trust for products and documents – Guidelines for securing physical documents
ISO 22392:2020	Security and resilience – Community resilience – Guidelines for conducting peer reviews
ISO 22393:2023	Security and resilience – Community resilience – Guidelines for planning recovery and renewal
ISO 22395:2018	Security and resilience – Community resilience – Guidelines for supporting vulnerable persons in an emergency
ISO 22396:2020	Security and resilience – Community resilience – Guidelines for information exchange between organizations
ISO 22397:2014	Societal security – Guidelines for establishing partnering arrangements
ISO 22398:2013	Societal security – Guidelines for exercises
ISO 28000:2022	Security and resilience – Security management systems – Requirements

ISO 28001:2007	Security management systems for the supply chain — Best practices for implementing supply chain security, assessments and plans — Requirements and guidance
ISO 28002:2011	Security management systems for the supply chain — Development of resilience in the supply chain — Requirements with guidance for use
ISO 28003:2007	Security management systems for the supply chain — Requirements for bodies providing audit and certification of supply chain security management systems
ISO 28004-1:2007	Security management systems for the supply chain — Guidelines for the implementation of ISO 28000 — Part 1: General principles
ISO 28004-3:2014	Security management systems for the supply chain — Guidelines for the implementation of ISO 28000 — Part 3: Additional specific guidance for adopting ISO 28000 for use by medium and small businesses (other than marine ports)
ISO 28004-4:2014	Security management systems for the supply chain — Guidelines for the implementation of ISO 28000 — Part 4: Additional specific guidance on implementing ISO 28000 if compliance with ISO 28001 is a management objective
ISO 28004-1:2007/Cor 1:2012	Security management systems for the supply chain — Guidelines for the implementation of ISO 28000 — Part 1: General principles — Technical Corrigendum 1

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